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PATIENT SATISFACTION WITH ANESTHETIC CARE: WHAT DO WE KNOW?

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Patient satisfaction with anesthesia care (PSAC) impacts perceived quality of anesthesia care and may be linked to reimbursement, provider competency evaluations, and litigation. The purpose of this doctoral project was to examine published PSAC evidence in order to conceptualize it, identify modifiable factors related to it, and provide recommendations for providers which may enhance PSAC.

Limited to English articles published within the last 20 years, the evidence search for articles focused on those with data and conceptualizations of PSAC and excluded those only addressing PSAC in pediatrics and obstetrics. Multiple sources were searched including Google Scholar, Pubmed, Cinahl, Business (EBSCO), ABI Inform Complete and Science Direct. Publications found included systematic reviews, reports from surveys, reports from qualitative data, and consumer satisfaction articles. From these, articles from 27 quantitative studies, seven qualitative studies, and nine consumer satisfaction commentaries were selected for analysis.

Prior patient experiences, colored or mediated by patient emotions, along with the realities of a current experience impacts how patients perceive or remember their overall anesthetic experience. The sum of the anesthetic experience includes the encounter with the anesthetist, the actual anesthesia experience, as well as the postoperative experience.

Few measures for PSAC were found. Development and psychometric analysis of PSAC measures varied across studies and often lacked rigor. Despite this, documented

PSAC was high across all sources of evidence. Modifiable patient dissatisfiers include preoperative anxiety, inadequate anesthesia explanation, long wait times, pain, nausea and vomiting, long surgeries, and anesthesia complications. Studies evaluating patient perioperative experiences document that fear and anxiety related to prior patient experience impacts anticipatory anxiety. Patients desire positive experiences and an emotional connection with anesthesia providers.

Developed within this project, the Anesthesia Patient Satisfaction Model shows several modifiable factors that can be addressed by anesthesiologists. For example, anesthesiologists must consider the impact of patient emotions as a filter through which anesthesia expectations are formed; emotions such as anxiety and fear require provider attention in order to mitigate patient dissatisfaction.

In addition to providing information, setting reasonable expectations for things such as nausea and vomiting, and adequately treating discomfort/pain, anesthesia providers must engage emotionally with patients. Future qualitative research addressing patient experiences with differing types of anesthesia would be insightful in furthering comprehension regarding these potentially stressful patient experiences. In clinical settings, using a standardized measure of PSAC that includes the emotional component of PSAC may offer a more accurate appraisal of patient experiences. Educators may consider developing anesthesia simulation or role play exercises that use a highly anxious preoperative patient in an effort to effectively prepare providers for addressing these patients before surgery.

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BACKGROUND

In the course of any given year, full-time anesthetists can deliver over 1000 anesthetics to surgical patients, including general anesthesia, regional anesthesia, monitored anesthesia care, or a combination of both regional and general anesthesia (Hogan, Seifert, Moore, & Simonson, 2010). After each surgery, anesthetists bring patients to the recovery room for post-anesthesia care. Upon assessing vital signs, ensuring patient comfort, and reporting to the recovery room nurse, they perform a preoperative assessment on the next patient and return into the operating room to begin again. Given this cycle, insight into patient satisfaction with anesthetic care (PSAC) is often lost or not reliably evaluated; patients go home or are transferred to hospital beds. In most institutions, anesthetists receive reports of patient dissatisfaction with anesthesia only in the event of an untoward outcome. Given that patient perspective provides a foundational marker for quality improvement measurements, anesthetists must be aware of patient opinions about their surgical and anesthesia experience.

Problem Significance

Quality Improvement and Safety

Current research documents objective outcomes (e.g., pain, nausea) related to PSAC (Capuzzo & Alvisi, 2008). Patient satisfaction and quality of anesthesia care, however, also depend upon the thoughts, feelings, and values of patients (Capuzzo & Alvisi, 2008). These subjective factors are difficult to measure and may not be reflected in current practice indicators.

Patient perceptions of satisfaction with anesthesia care are affected greatly by lack of understanding of the role of anesthetists (Bloomberg, 2014). Preoperative

communication from anesthesiologists outlining anesthesia options and postoperative expectations can not only alleviate anxiety, but offers patients a sense of control over their care (Bloomberg, 2014). This preparation allows patients involvement in their care and provides opportunities for error reduction. Patient education and perioperative communication as to surgical site markings, potential postoperative complications, complications of comorbid conditions, and allergy reactions aid in obtaining high care quality; good communication, and patient preparation can also lead to patient trust with providers and subsequently, improve post-operative satisfaction and error reduction (Bloomberg, 2014). As a result, measures to improve PSAC are intertwined with quality improvement and safety measures.

Reimbursements

The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) in collaboration with the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) standardized patient satisfaction metrics by recommending use of the Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (CAHPS) and the Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) (Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services [CMS], 2014). Since 2008, in an effort to improve healthcare quality, CMS has used these surveys to calculate value-based payments. Beginning in 2012, the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act also included HCAHPS results for incentive payment calculations. Survey results were coupled with annual payment updates so that hospitals must report HCAHPS results to receive payment. Hospitals subjected to inpatient prospective payment systems (IPPS) that failed to report HCAHPS results experience a 2% reduction in reimbursements (Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services, 2014). These payment trends (e.g.,

reimbursement tied to satisfaction) indicate that patient satisfaction surveys may eventually be used in calculating anesthesia reimbursements in the future.

Competency and Performance

Given that reimbursements are linked to satisfaction survey results, many hospitals measure performance and competency based on patient satisfaction survey results. These survey results may affect personnel performance evaluations that in turn, influence compensation. Additionally, the American Board of Medical Specialty as well as the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education include patient perspectives from survey results to assess practitioner communication skills (Koch, 2014). Results may coalesce as part of a practice performance assessment for graduating medical students.

Litigation

While some hospital administrators include patient satisfaction survey results in evaluations of anesthetist performance, patients assess anesthetists when deciding upon litigation (Fullam, 2010). Forming positive relationships with patients prior, during, and after surgery helps mitigate litigation. Newer research supports this correlation between malpractice suits and patient dissatisfaction (Fullam, 2010). An analysis of Press Ganey satisfaction surveys using hierarchical linear modeling examined risks of litigation and patient perspectives of providers between 1998 to 2006. Providers rated as “very good” had no filed lawsuits (0% risk of litigation) which is contrasted with providers rated as “very poor” who had up to a 20% chance risk of litigation (Fullam, 2010, pp. 2-3).

Problem Statement

Given the impact of patient satisfaction surveys on reimbursement, competency and litigation, as well as provider responsibility to provide positive, safe and ethical experiences for patients, anesthesiologists must understand and mitigate the modifiable factors that may impact and improve patient satisfaction with anesthesia care. An understanding of modifiable factors requires an examination of measures of patient satisfaction in addition to an exploration of patient-related factors that may impact satisfaction (e.g., prior surgeries, comorbid conditions, learning needs, health literacy). Other modifiable factors affecting patient perceptions of satisfaction with anesthesia care include individual provider personal characteristics and types/quality of communication between anesthesiologists and patients.

Supporting Framework

Patients are considered consumers of medical/nursing care. This idea points to the need for recognition and understanding of customer satisfaction models. Several consumer satisfaction models from marketing research provide strong frameworks that translate well into healthcare and patient satisfaction. The disconfirmation theory developed by Richard Oliver offers a widely referenced and accepted theory of customer satisfaction (Newsome & Wright, 1999). Disconfirmation reflects the balance between consumer expectations of service and perceived performance (Liu & Zhao, 2009). Perceived performance can be distinguished from actual or technical performance when the consumer is not familiar with the service (Hom, 2000). A conceptual model that allows for a dynamic expression of satisfaction as a changing process dependent upon a feedback loop is shown below.

Figure 1. An adapted model of disconfirmation theory by Bateson that reflects the dynamic nature of satisfaction and includes a differentiation between technical or actual service and perceived service (Hom, 2000).

This model underscores the relationship between patient expectations with perceived service as part of an interdependent loop shaping feelings of satisfaction. Additionally, it takes into account prior patient experiences as well as provider influence. Inputs or comparison standards such as type of surgery, previous anesthetic experiences, comorbid conditions, learning or literacy needs, and health care values all shape patient expectations prior to surgery.

Personal contact through provider interaction plays an important role in influencing satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Findings from a study by Linder-Peltz on expectations and perceptions related to satisfaction with health care show that while expectations, values and perceptions shape patient satisfaction, patient beliefs about the provider and provider performance play an even larger role (as cited in Newsome & Wright, 1999). These findings highlight the importance of anesthetist knowledge of patient expectations as well as the importance of the preoperative evaluation in determining patient satisfaction.

Objective measures such as actual performance and technical quality of care contribute to perceived levels of satisfaction through a subjective measure (Newsome & Wright, 1999). Patients judge the technical quality of care as well as the competence of providers based on their perceptions (Newsome & Wright, 1999). Anesthesia care that meets or exceeds the American Association of Nurse Anesthesia standard may or may not influence patient perception of care, yet care below the standard, resulting in untoward outcomes, can negatively influence patient perspectives of perceived service resulting in dissatisfaction.

The disconfirmation model suggests that all of these comparison standards shape customer--or patient--evaluations of perceived performance which in turn influences satisfaction (Hom, 2000). The higher the consumer expectations, the less likely the actual service can meet those expectations and lead to feelings of dissatisfaction. Consequently, an understanding of the relationships between patient expectations, provider interaction, actual service, and perceived service as a dynamic feedback loop shaping feelings of satisfaction establishes a framework that may aid anesthesiologists in identifying and influencing the modifiable factors related to satisfaction with anesthesia care.

Project Purpose

The purpose of this project was to examine current literature to uncover metrics of patient satisfaction specific to anesthesia care as well as to identify the modifiable factors related to satisfaction with anesthesia care. Examination of modifiable factors was done in the context of a clear understanding of the concept of patient satisfaction, confounding factors such as types and number of prior patient surgeries, comorbid conditions, patient

learning needs along with trends in health literacy, provider personal characteristics, as well as the survey instrument used to evaluate patient satisfaction.

The compilation of findings into a manuscript submitted for publication in the *AANA Journal* reflected the proposed project outcome. Publication in the *AANA Journal* impacts a multitude of anesthetists and provides a large forum for enhanced awareness of issues surrounding this topic. Publication in the *AANA Journal* additionally offers an avenue for provider education regarding strategies to enhance patient satisfaction with anesthesia. The aim of the project manuscript was to explore and define the concept of patient satisfaction with anesthesia care, examine and evaluate existing patient satisfaction surveys, synthesize satisfaction survey findings, and provide recommendations for anesthesia providers to enhance patient satisfaction in the work place. In that there are no standard measurements of PSAC to date, an examination of available evidence with the goal of providing findings and recommendations to a multitude of providers yielded the best method of implementing quality improvement at the institutional level (See Appendix A & B).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Methods

In order to ensure a comprehensive literature review of PSAC, key terms, topics, databases, as well as search limits are identified, listed and presented in Table 1.

Additionally, reference lists from articles related to patient satisfaction with anesthesia were reviewed and searched. Relevant research articles included within systematic reviews were also included.

Table 1

Search Methods

Database	Topic(s)	Key Terms	Limits
Pubmed® Google Scholar Cinahl ScienceDirect®	Psychometric testing – patient satisfaction	Anesthesia “Patient satisfaction” Surveys or questionnaires	English, German only. Includes qualitative and quantitative (RCT descriptive observational, cohort, cross-sectional and survey) research, systematic reviews, reviews of literature.
	Quantitative studies patient satisfaction	Perioperative (All combinations of these four key terms) Patient satisfaction AND surveys AND anesthesia (all combinations) Patient satisfaction AND questionnaires AND anesthesia (all combinations) Perioperative patient satisfaction AND surveys AND anesthesia Perioperative patient satisfaction AND questionnaires AND anesthesia	
	Qualitative studies patient satisfaction	Anesthesia Patient satisfaction Patient experience Perioperative Qualitative Patient satisfaction with anesthesia qualitative studies Perioperative patient satisfaction with anesthesia qualitative studies	Includes patient satisfaction with general, regional, local anesthesia and sedation. Excludes pediatric, obstetric anesthesia.
Business (EBSCO) ABI/Inform Complete	Consumer satisfaction	Disconfirmation theory Marketing theory Consumer satisfaction Customer satisfaction Consumer satisfaction AND healthcare Patient satisfaction AND anesthesia	Marketing research publication dates from 2005-2015. English language only.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the search followed a systematic approach. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are listed in Table 1. As shown in Figure 3, the search of marketing research literature generated nine articles that included the disconfirmation model of consumer satisfaction. Articles were reviewed for relevance and applicability and excluded when deemed irrelevant.

Figure 2. Cumulative literature search from Pubmed, Google Scholar, CINAHL.

Figure 3. Cumulative literature search of consumer satisfaction using disconfirmation model from Business Source Premier (EBSCO) and ABI/Inform Complete (Proquest).

Measuring Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care

The evidence found was used for the development of a manuscript related to PSAC. The literature search yielded 41 research studies or reviews (see Appendix C).

Definitions of Patient Satisfaction

An exploration of concept analyses (Eriksen, 1995; Wagner & Bear, 2008) offers insight for a definition and clarification of patient satisfaction. Taxonomies of patient satisfaction with care include dimensions such as care thoroughness, giving/receiving information, and provider characteristics: courtesy, concern, respect and demeanor (Eriksen, 1995). Antecedents of satisfaction include social influences, patient characteristics, prior experiences with healthcare (e.g., surgery/anesthesia), environmental influences, and cognitive status as well as affective responses related to the care experience (Eriksen, 1995; Wagner & Bear, 2008). Most descriptions of patient satisfaction with care delivery describe a link between patient satisfaction and

expectations (Eriksen, 1995). That is, patients compare the actual care experience with a subjective standard or expectation. As a result, patient satisfaction includes emotional responses generated from cognitive processes comparing an actual experience to prior expectations (Eriksen, 1995).

Capuzzo and Alvisi (2008) define patient satisfaction as a comparison between patient expectations and outcomes. Though patient satisfaction hinges on patient values and perceptions, its measurement is often assessed objectively using survey methods with no attempt to gain open-ended patient comments (Capuzzo & Alvisi, 2008). Survey methods use questioning to obtain self-reported information about beliefs, feelings and attitudes as well as preferences (Polit & Beck, 2012). Given that each survey used to assess patient satisfaction addresses the concept of patient satisfaction differently, an operational definition of patient satisfaction then becomes an objective measure of outcomes limited by the specific questions within each survey

Documented Psychometrics

Systematic reviews. The current literature search yielded six systematic reviews regarding PSAC as well as one Cochrane review. The systematic reviews about patient satisfaction focus primarily on psychometric testing of measures, but reveal high levels of PSAC overall (Barnett et al., 2013b; Le May, Hardy, Taillefer, & Dupuis, 2000). Patients reported their satisfaction with anesthesia care from immediately after surgery to several months postoperatively using mail-back questionnaires, face-to-face interviews, phone interviews, or a combination (Barnett et al., 2013b; Chanthong, Abrishami, Wong, Herrera, & Chung, 2009; D. Fung & Cohen, 1998; Le May et al., 2000).

Cross-sectional surveys using a Likert response format form the bases of most measures of PSAC. Few primary studies reviewed contained rigorous psychometric testing (Barnett et al., 2013b; Bell, Halliburton, & Preston, 2004; Chanthong et al., 2009; D. Fung & Cohen, 1998; Gurusamy, Vaughan, & Davidson, 2014; R. Hawkins, Swanson, & Kremer, 2012; Le May et al., 2000). Barnett et al. (2013) reviewed over 3000 articles with a patient satisfaction outcome and found only 71 that reported psychometric testing of the patient satisfaction measure. Specific to anesthesia care, Bell et al. (2004), Le May et al. (2000), and Fung and Cohen (1998) report high likelihood of measurement error across studies, limited psychometric testing, and no control for confounding variables. Le May et al. (2000) additionally address time sensitivity as a barrier to reliability testing. Patient satisfaction measures may not be reliable in test-retest reliability and as a result may not measure patient perceptions accurately.

Despite the reported lack of rigor in the development of patient satisfaction measures, Hawkins et al. (2012), Chanthong et al. (2009) and Le May et al. (2000) disclosed common factors (inputs) affecting patient satisfaction: Information, pain, postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV), wait times, interpersonal skills of providers, privacy, safety, continuity of care, emergence and awareness (see Appendix D). Though Hawkins et al. (2012) and Chanthong et al. (2009) reported the provision of information to patients as a modifiable factor predictive of patient satisfaction, Gurusamy et al. (Gurusamy et al., 2014), in a Cochrane review of clinical trials of education in laparoscopy, found no clear evidence that patient education improves patient satisfaction.

Individual studies measuring patient satisfaction. Across 27 studies measuring patient satisfaction, 23 provided information regarding psychometric testing of surveys

(see Table 3) (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi, Nofal, & Ahmad, 2010; Bauer, Bohrer, Aichele, Bach, & Martin, 2001; Caljouw, van Beuzekom, & Boer, 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Dexter, Aker, & Wright, 1997; Fleisher et al., 1999; Flierler, Nübling, Kasper, & Heidegger, 2013; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; A. D. Fung et al., 2001; Gebremedhn & Nagarathnam, 2014; R. Hawkins et al., 2012; Hocking, Weightman, Smith, Gibbs, & Sherrard, 2013; S. Iravani et al., 2012; Maurice-Szamburski, Bruder, Loundou, Capdevila, & Auquier, 2013; McCarthy, Trigg, John, Gough, & Horrocks, 2004; Mitchell, 2011; Mui et al., 2011; Myles, Williams, Hendrata, Anderson, & Weeks, 2000; Puro, Pakarinen, Korttila, & Tallgren, 2013; Royse, Chung, Newman, Stygall, & Wilkinson, 2013; Saal, Heidegger, Nuebling, & Germann, 2011; Schiff et al., 2008).

In 19 studies, overall PSAC was rated as high (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al., 2001; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Dexter et al., 1997; Fleisher et al., 1999; Flierler et al., 2013; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; D. Fung & Cohen, 2001; Gebremedhn & Nagarathnam, 2014; R. Hawkins, Swanson, Kremer, & Fogg, 2014; Hocking et al., 2013; S. Iravani et al., 2012; Jlala, Caljouw, Bedford, & Hardman, 2010; Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; McCarthy et al., 2004; Puro et al., 2013; Royse et al., 2013; Saal et al., 2011; Sindhvananda, Leelanukrom, & Juajarungjai, 2003).

As listed in Table 2, 16 of the 23 studies offered specific information regarding instrument validity and reliability (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al., 2001; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Dexter et al., 1997; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Hocking et al., 2013; Jlala et al., 2010; Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; McCarthy

et al., 2004; Mitchell, 2011; Mui et al., 2011; Puro et al., 2013; Schiff et al., 2008; Sindhvananda et al., 2003).

Table 2

Instrument Validity and Reliability

Author	IV	EV	DV	CV	NV	CoV	FV	R
Auquier et al., 2005		✓	✓					Internal consistency or α
Baroudi et al., 2010	✓			✓		✓	✓	Test-retest
Bauer et al., 2001				✓				Test-retest Internal consistency or α
Caljow et al., 2008			✓	✓		✓		Internal consistency or α
Capuzzo et al., 2005				✓				Internal consistency or α Inter-rater
Dexter et al., 1997						✓		Test-retest
Hawkins et al., 2014				✓				
Hocking et al., 2013				✓				Test-retest
Jlala et al., 2010			✓					Internal consistency or α
Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013	✓	✓	✓			✓		Internal consistency
McCarthy et al., 2004			✓	✓	✓	✓		
Mitchel, 2011			✓	✓	✓	✓		
Mui et al., 2011			✓	✓	✓	✓		
Puro et al., 2013								Internal consistency or α
Schiff et al., 2008		✓	✓	✓				Internal consistency or α
Sindhvananda et al., 2013		✓	✓	✓				Internal consistency or α

Note. CV = content validity, CoV = convergent validity, DV = discriminant validity, EV = external validity, FV = face validity, IV = internal validity, NV = nomological validity, R = reliability.

Of the 16 studies yielding psychometric information, no standard survey for PSAC emerged. In each study, different survey instruments were developed or used. Dexter et al. (1997) developed the Iowa Satisfaction with Anesthesia Scale (ISAS), which was widely used and adapted. The ISAS survey was cited or referenced within 11 of the psychometric survey articles (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al.,

2001; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Fleisher et al., 1999; Hocking et al., 2013; Mui et al., 2011; Myles et al., 2000; Schiff et al., 2008; Sindhvananda et al., 2003).

It was also included or referenced in six systematic reviews (Barnett et al., 2013; Bell et al., 2004; Chanthong et al., 2009; D. Fung & Cohen, 1998; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Mui et al., 2011). Dexter et al. (1997) surveyed English-speaking patients undergoing monitored anesthesia care (MAC) admitted to the post anesthesia care unit. Baroudi et al. (2010) then modified the ISAS by translating it into Arabic and adapting the original questions so that they appropriately represent the Arabic culture. Dexter et al. (1997) developed the ISAS for MAC anesthesia exclusively; however, Baroudi et al. (2010) adapted and used a modified version of this survey to determine patient satisfaction for patients receiving MAC, regional, and general anesthesia.

Though some survey instruments were adapted and used to generate patient satisfaction results, no previously developed and validated survey instrument was used to generate outcomes. A survey developed for French-speaking patients and adapted for regional anesthesia, the Evaluation du Vécu de l'Anesthésie LocoRégionale (EVAN-LR), measures patient satisfaction with regional anesthesia and is intended to be used from 4 to 48 hours after surgery (Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013). First developed for general anesthesia, the original EVAN-G included 26 items (Auquier et al., 2005). Caljouw et al. (2008) expanded the EVAN to include questions about information given, patient involvement, and patient information, calling it the Leiden Perioperative care Patient Satisfaction questionnaire (LPPSq); it was translated into English and revalidated by Jlala et al. (2010). The EVAN-LR (Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013) and EVAN-G along with the ISAS (Dexter et al., 1997) were used for comparison during the development of

the Perioperative Anesthetic Care questionnaire (PSPACq) developed by Mui et al. (2011).

Hawkins et al. (2014), Hocking et al. (2013), Mui et al. (2011), and McCarthy et al. (2004) developed instruments specific to patient satisfaction for patients undergoing either regional or general anesthesia. McCarthy et al. (2004) developed the Specific Carotid Endarterectomy Experience Questionnaire (CEA-EQ) measuring satisfaction of patients undergoing carotid endarterectomy under either regional or general anesthesia. Hawkins et al. (2014) generated survey content following an integrated review of studies and plan to develop a psychometric instrument in a future study. Hocking et al. (2013) measured patient satisfaction with general and regional anesthesia from the patient's perspective. Mui et al. (2011) developed a survey based on items from both the ISAS and EVAN-LR for general and regional anesthesia in Taiwanese patients. Several other researchers developed or adapted a variety of different survey instruments; however, few documented psychometric testing (Fleisher et al., 1999; Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014; Hadjistavropoulos, Dobson, & Boisvert, 2001; Hering, Harvan, D'Angelo, & Jasinkski, 2005; S. Iravani et al., 2012; Puro et al., 2013; Saal et al., 2011).

Overall Findings About Psychometrics

Polit and Beck (2012) define validity in the context of psychometric testing as the degree that an item or instrument measures what it intends to measure. Content validity represents the degree that the survey questions adequately represent the construct domain (Polit & Beck, 2012). The authors report content validity in 10 of 16 studies as listed in Table 2 (Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al., 2001; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Hocking et al., 2013; McCarthy et al., 2004; Mitchell,

2011; Mui et al., 2011; Sindhvananda et al., 2003). In five studies, content validity was established using the judgment of an expert panel of anesthetists (Bauer et al., 2001; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Hocking et al., 2013; Mitchell, 2011; Sindhvananda et al., 2003). Hawkins et al. (2014) calculated a content validity index requiring the expert panel to rate individual questions against the overall instrument to determine if the questions effectively sum up the construct dimensions (Polit & Beck, 2012). Similarly, Capuzzo et al. (2005) compared measurements examining logical relationships between items and patient characteristics.

Mui et al. (2011) and Caljouw et al. (2008) used an exploratory factor analysis to identify the underlying construct dimensions that provide the foundation for survey question development. Mui et al. (2011) additionally validated and cross validated their survey questionnaire for both regional and general anesthesia. Their findings offer strong evidence supporting validity (Mui et al., 2011). They looked further for associations between patient satisfaction with regional or general anesthesia and loyalty (predictive validity) and found positive correlations that support nomological validity of patient satisfaction (Mui et al., 2011). Baroudi et al. (2010) reported good content validity; the authors concluded this based solely on comments offered by patients (Baroudi et al., 2010). McCarthy et al. (2004) evaluated convergent validity between anxiety and patient satisfaction generated from their questionnaire with the State Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI-S) and Satisfaction with Surgical Services Questionnaire (SSSQ).

Dexter, Aker, and Wright (1997) describe good convergent validity through the correlation of scores generated by the ISAS with scores predicted by an observer. The authors, however, did not provide further information regarding the observer (Dexter et

al., 1997). Maurice-Szamburski et al. (2013) and Caljouw et al. (2008) also claim good convergent validity through factor analysis. Maurice-Szamburski et al. (2013) conducted a dimension correlation with previously validated instruments such as the Amsterdam Preoperative Anxiety and Information Scale, State Trait Anxiety Inventory and visual analog scales. Caljouw et al. (2008) correlated the incidence of adverse anesthesia outcomes with type of surgery, scale dimensions, and reports of pain, nausea, vomiting and discomfort.

When reported, satisfaction measures had adequate validity, but reporting was inadequate for most measures. Additionally, differing methods of reliability testing coupled with inadequate validity reporting create further untrustworthiness of the findings about PSAC. Reliability reflects the consistency of a measure to adequately reflect an attribute (Polit & Beck, 2012). Polit and Beck (2012) claim that instruments without reliability are also without validity. That is, the reliability of an instrument can exist independently from validity such that the instrument does not accurately measuring the construct (Polit & Beck, 2012). Twelve authors of 23 report adequate reliability (see Table 2) (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al., 2001; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Dexter et al., 1997; Hocking et al., 2013; Jlala et al., 2010; Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; Puro et al., 2013; Schiff et al., 2008; Sindhvananda et al., 2003). Four articles report good test-retest reliability (Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al., 2001; Dexter et al., 1997; Hocking et al., 2013). A value for Cronbach's alpha was calculated in nine articles as a measure of the instrument's reliability (Auquier et al., 2005; Bauer et al., 2001; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Jlala et al., 2010;

Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; Puro et al., 2013; Schiff et al., 2008; Sindhvananda et al., 2003). All nine articles claim high Cronbach's alpha values.

In an earlier systematic review addressing psychometric instrument evaluations of 14 studies, LeMay et al. (2000) claim questionable survey validity and reliability due to lack of control for confounding variables, varied psychometric testing procedures, bias, and no conceptual framework. Similarly, Barnett et al. (2013) found that of 3000 articles claiming patient satisfaction as an outcome, only 71 included psychometric testing. They found bias inherent in all 71 studies along with inconsistencies in testing methods and timing of testing. In a survey of 11 primary studies, Chanthong et al. (2009) concluded a need for further psychometric studies with increased rigor due to varied testing measures and limited discussion of item generation. LeMay et al. (2000) note that most studies claim high levels of patient satisfaction, but few authors question this.

Specific Items in Patient Satisfaction Surveys

In each study that included measures of patient satisfaction with anesthesia, methods for item generation differed. In eight studies, researchers generated items using an expert panel (Auquier et al., 2005; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Dexter et al., 1997; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Mitchell, 2011; Mui et al., 2011; Schiff et al., 2008). Hocking et al. (2013), Caljouw et al. (2008), Auquier et al. (2005), Sindhvananda et al. (2003) and Fung and Cohen (2001) developed questions through personal interviews with patients. Maurice-Szamburski et al. (2013), Fraczyk and Godfrey (2010) as well as McCarthy et al. (2004) developed items based on a previously conducted qualitative study. All of these methods support content validity of the survey instruments (Polit & Beck, 2012). Uniquely, Gebremedhn and Nagaratnam (2014) generated items using a

hospital anesthetic evaluation sheet. Item generation methods were not reported in 11 studies (Bauer et al., 2001; Fleisher et al., 1999; Flierler et al., 2013; Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001; Hering et al., 2005; S. Iravani et al., 2012; Jlala et al., 2010; Myles et al., 2000; Puro et al., 2013; Royse et al., 2013; Saal et al., 2011).

The specific questions and items used in surveys to measure patient satisfaction were included in 10 studies (Caljouw et al., 2008; Dexter et al., 1997; A. D. Fung et al., 2001; Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014; Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Jlala et al., 2010; Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; Mui et al., 2011; Schiff et al., 2008) (see Appendix E). In all 10 surveys, a Likert-type response set was used for individual items. All 10 included questions about pain, postoperative nausea and vomiting, anxiety, and overall satisfaction. Surveys in Hawkins et al. (2014), Jlala et al. (2010) Mui et al. (2011), Schiff et al. (2008), Fung and Cohen (2001) and Hadjistavropoulos et al. (2001) contained comprehensive, detailed questions whereas Dexter et al. (1997), Caljouw et al. (2010), Maurice-Szamburski et al. (2013) and Gebremedhn and Nagaratnam (2014) included short sentences or incomplete phrases (see Appendix E).

Procedures Used to Measure Patient Satisfaction

Consistent with the results from systematic reviews conducted by Chanthong et al. (2009) and Le May et al. (2000), data capture differed or was not described in all studies. Patients might be interviewed, receive a mailed survey, or be provided with a handout provided by anesthesia providers or another, as well as various combinations. Thus, the relationship of survey to timing from the surgical experience varied across studies from 0 hours (immediately after surgery in the PACU) to days afterward for

mailed surveys. The authors reported little regarding how questions were answered or in what context, increasing the likelihood of bias. In that test-retest reliability is sensitive to time, patient satisfaction results may change over time and may not be pertinent for the construct of PSAC (Le May et al., 2000; Royse et al., 2013). Despite this, as seen in Table 2, four studies reported good test-retest reliabilities for the ISAS and Patient Perception of Quality of Anesthesia Care (PQA) (Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al., 2001; Dexter et al., 1997; Hocking et al., 2013).

Inconsistencies in item generation, survey development and testing as well as evaluation methods limit the comparability of the results. Interestingly, only eight of the 27 studies offered a definition of patient satisfaction (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi et al., 2010; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Jlala et al., 2010; Sindhvananda et al., 2003).

Findings about Patient Satisfaction

Across the studies, overall PSAC was high and only one researcher questioned this (Le May et al., 2000). Though the strength of the initial evidence provides little reassurance of adequate or accurate measures of patient satisfaction, several common themes related to dissatisfiers, satisfiers, and confounding variables emerged (see Appendix D).

Patient Dissatisfiers

The collective evidence supports postoperative nausea, vomiting, and pain as major contributors to decreased patient satisfaction scores. Other factors include fear, anxiety, postoperative complications, lack of inclusion of patients in the decision-making process, age (younger), education (higher), gender (females), type of surgery, American

Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) I or II, preoperative wait times (longer), alcohol habits (non-drinkers), and experiencing awareness under anesthesia (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi et al., 2010; Bauer et al., 2001; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Dexter et al., 1997; Fleisher et al., 1999; Flierler et al., 2013; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; D. Fung & Cohen, 2001; Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014; Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Hocking et al., 2013; S. Iravani et al., 2012; Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; McCarthy et al., 2004; Mitchell, 2011; Mui et al., 2011; Myles et al., 2000; Puro et al., 2013; Royse et al., 2013; Saal et al., 2011; Schiff et al., 2008). Additionally, Hocking et al. (2013), Royse et al. (2013), Schiff et al. (2008), and Myles et al. (2000) claim increased surgery length contributes to patient dissatisfaction (see Appendix D).

Royse et al. (2013) included time as a factor in patient perceptions of satisfaction. Patient satisfaction and post-operative recovery were measured at 15 minutes, 40 minutes, one to three days postoperatively, and three months postoperatively. While high proportions of patients were completely satisfied with their anesthesia care (83%) on day 3, patients not totally satisfied with anesthesia care often reported postoperative nausea and vomiting (Royse et al., 2013). Following a multivariable logistic regression of the significant univariate predictors, Royse et al. (2013) identified four independent predictors of less than total satisfaction: pain and nausea on postoperative day three, dissatisfaction at day one, postoperative pain and nausea at 15 minutes and on day one. Counter-intuitively, pain and nausea at 15 minutes and day one postoperatively led to increased satisfaction with anesthesia care (Royse et al., 2013). Royse et al. thought the survey timing may have contributed to these results. Overall satisfaction decreased from

75% of patients at discharge to 62% of patients at 30 days postoperatively. The three-month postoperative results were not reported (Royse et al., 2013).

Patient Satisfiers

Across much of the literature, patient satisfaction scores were higher when providers communicated risks, benefits, alternative anesthesia options, and answered questions prior to patients receiving anesthesia than when providers did not communicate or answer questions. Similarly, patients reported higher levels of satisfaction when engaged and included by the anesthetist in pre-operative decision-making than when not included (Baroudi et al., 2010; Flierler et al., 2013; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Hocking et al., 2013; Puro et al., 2013). Patients reported decreased feelings of anxiety after speaking with anesthesia providers prior to surgery (Baroudi et al., 2010; Caljouw et al., 2008; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014; R. Hawkins et al., 2014; Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; McCarthy et al., 2004; Mitchell, 2011; Mui et al., 2011; Royse et al., 2013; Schiff et al., 2008). Additionally, Hawkins et al. (2014) and Hocking et al. (2013) reported lower levels of anxiety and higher patient satisfaction scores for higher levels of reported provider kindness and gentleness.

Saal et al. (2011) addressed continuity of care as a method to increase patient satisfaction, defining continuity of care as occurring when a single provider performs the preoperative evaluation, provides surgical anesthesia, and then visits the patient postoperatively (Saal et al., 2011). In a study of 642 patients undergoing elective surgery who were randomized into three groups, Saal et al. (2011) assessed whether a postoperative visit increased patient satisfaction scores. Group 1 had a postoperative visit

from the anesthetist providing the surgical anesthesia. Group 2 received a postoperative visit from an anesthetist not providing anesthesia. Group 3 had no postoperative visit (Saal et al., 2011). Questionnaires were sent home with patients prior to discharge. Saal et al. (2011) created a negative problem score from the scores generated by not being visited by an anesthetist postoperatively. The scores from the other two groups were then compared with the problem score. Saal et al. (2011) also compared the effect of the problem score with patient continuity of care scores and overall dissatisfaction with anesthesia care. Saal et al. (2011) discovered that continuity of care increases patient satisfaction scores with anesthesia care; both groups of patients who received visits were more satisfied than were patients who did not receive a visit, but the two visited groups did not differ.

Experiences in the recovery room can also impact patient satisfaction with anesthesia care. Baroudi et al. (2010) reported that perceptions of good post anesthesia care were associated with higher levels of patient satisfaction

Confounding Factors

Confounding variables were addressed in five studies (Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013; Mui et al., 2011; Royse et al., 2013; Saal et al., 2011; Schiff et al., 2008):

- Patient anxiety, surgical outcomes and anesthesia medication effects (Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013).
- Wide age range (Royse et al., 2013).
- Age, sex, educational level, anesthesia type, type of surgery and loyalty (Mui et al., 2011).

In fact, Mui et al. (2011) showed predictable patterns among these variables and dimensions of satisfaction through a confounding variable analysis. Older men with primary school education receiving general anesthesia had higher satisfaction scores than did other patients. Schiff et al. (2008) similarly conducted a confounding variable analysis, but did not report the specific confounding variables. Saal et al. (2011) disclosed higher reports of dissatisfaction with patients of ASA I or II level and higher educational level. Maurice-Szamburski et al. (2013) claimed that patient anxiety negatively influenced PSAC scores. Anxious patients reported higher dissatisfaction with pain and postoperative nausea and vomiting (Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013).

Studies that take into account such confounding factors provide greater statistical control, enhancing validity and managing bias (Polit & Beck, 2012).

Provider Performance Improvement

Hocking et al. (2013) conducted a unique study assessing whether patient satisfaction scores would positively impact the behavior of anesthetists. The researchers used face-to-face interviews and an investigator-developed e-mail questionnaire as a performance improvement measure for PSAC. Feedback from the first patient satisfaction survey was then given to anesthesia providers. Following a new cohort of patients given face-to-face interviews and e-mail questionnaires, results were compared. The post-feedback group of patients received more antiemetic therapy indicating a provider behavior change; patient satisfaction was not reported in the post-feedback cohort (Hocking et al., 2013).

Patient Perceptions

A preliminary literature search revealed seven qualitative studies that described patient experiences and perceptions related to anesthesia care. Studies exploring satisfaction with anesthesia include patient experiences with retinal eye surgery, hip or knee replacement surgery, general surgery, and experiences in the perioperative period. Patients in most studies expressed strong preoperative feelings of anxiety and fear (Costa, 2001; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; Hudson, Ogden, & Whiteley, 2015; McCloud, Harrington, & King, 2013; Susleck et al., 2007; Trängeberg & Stomberg, 2013; Webster, Bremner, & McCartney, 2011). Patients undergoing general anesthesia paradoxically reported high anxiety when being given information and when not being given enough information (Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010). Patients undergoing regional anesthesia showed decreased anxiety and increased satisfaction following a music intervention (Trängeberg & Stomberg, 2013). Patients expressed anxiety and multiple fears (e.g., of surgery, anesthesia, pain, being awake during surgery, helplessness, loss of control, death, of being cut) (Costa, 2001; McCloud et al., 2013; Susleck et al., 2007; Webster et al., 2011). Past patient experiences influenced anxiety levels.

Prior patient experience may impact patient anticipatory anxiety when general or regional anesthesia are being considered. Patients with positive prior experiences reported less and lower levels of anxiety (Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; McCloud et al., 2013; Webster et al., 2011). In a study describing patient experiences of having both regional and general anesthesia for hip/knee surgery (Webster et al., 2011), patients reported a preference for regional anesthesia if they had a prior negative experience with general anesthesia; however, in general, patients described greater fear and anxiety in

anticipation of regional anesthesia. Patients often preferred the anesthesia type recommended by the anesthetist or surgeon (Webster et al., 2011).

Across the qualitative studies, patients desired positive experiences with providers (Costa, 2001; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; Hudson et al., 2015; Susleck et al., 2007; Webster et al., 2011). Patients wanted to feel cared for and be known as unique persons throughout the perioperative period, into the operating room, and in recovery (Hudson et al., 2015). Anesthesia providers who listened, were attentive, showed supportive behaviors, answered questions, and provided anesthesia information generated emotional connections with patients that translated into patient satisfaction (Costa, 2001; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; Hudson et al., 2015; Susleck et al., 2007).

Consumer Satisfaction and Disconfirmation Theory

Marketing research extensively includes essential components that address the concept of consumer (e.g., patient) satisfaction. The disconfirmation theory as proposed by Oliver (1993) blends disconfirmation, or consumer expectation measured against actual performance, with an emotional response such as delight, excitement, anger and guilt as a determinant in shaping satisfaction. Prior experience, provider or employee affect, skill, time, products or outcomes, attributes and outside influences all shape consumer expectation (Barnes, Ponder, & Dugar, 2011; Bloemer & Dekker, 2007; Chih, Wang, Hsu, & Cheng, 2012; Ellis, Johnson, & Gudergan, 2005; Kanning & Bergmann, 2009; Kim, 2014; Moliner, 2008; Oliver, 1993; Trudel, Murray, & Cotte, 2011). The higher the consumer's expectation, the more difficult it will be to meet the expectation (Barnes et al., 2011; Chih et al., 2012; Ellis et al., 2005; Trudel et al., 2011). Conversely, high levels of performance (e.g., quality product or service) increase the likelihood of

increased satisfaction (Barnes et al., 2011; Chih et al., 2012; Ellis et al., 2005; Oliver, 1993; Trudel et al., 2011). Creating realistic expectations by deliberately reducing the service appeal, however, may also reduce the competitive attractiveness of a product (Newsome & Wright, 1999).

Chapter Summary

Though marketing research focuses specifically on consumer satisfaction with product or service, many concepts translate well into thoughts about PSAC. Although there were several commonalities and recurring themes, no single measure of PSAC emerged as superior to others. Difficulty in creating such an instrument may be due in part to concepts that emerge from marketing research. Patient satisfaction includes objective and subjective measures. Patient satisfaction with anesthesia care extends beyond reports from specific questions regarding measurable outcomes, but is affected by prior experiences, emotions, provider as well as patient affects and attributes, hospital aesthetics, in addition to quality of patient care.

A gap in the literature exists with regard to a conceptual and operational definition of patient satisfaction for both patients and providers. In addition, no cohesive model facilitating PSAC improvement exists. By exploring both marketing and PSAC research, findings from this project may bridge this gap.

METHODS

The project outcome consisted of a manuscript exploring the concept of PSAC and practice recommendations for anesthesia providers. The manuscript began with an introduction and background of the topic focusing on quality of care and safety. Patient satisfaction as it affects litigation, reimbursements and competency was also addressed and highlighted (See Appendix A).

A comprehensive literature review was done to examine the concept of adult and geriatric patient satisfaction with general anesthesia, regional anesthesia as well as monitored anesthesia care. Studies examining patient satisfaction with obstetric or pediatric care were not sought. The paucity of research as well as the added difficulty of assessing patient satisfaction in children precluded an accurate assessment of patient satisfaction (Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014). Patient satisfaction with obstetrical anesthesia may be influenced by the experience of childbirth projecting a multitude of confounding elements that may be best operationalized independently (Halls, 2008).

Patient satisfaction was operationalized based on thorough exploration of patient satisfaction research, patient satisfaction surveys, as well as consumer satisfaction research. Qualitative research was sought to lend depth and understanding to the description of this concept as well as insight into satisfiers/dissatisfiers for patients undergoing anesthesia. From the evidence synthesis, the Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care Model was developed.

Studies were evaluated to determine validity, reliability, and utility of patient satisfaction surveys described. Findings were integrated into a table for ease of comparison. Patient satisfaction concepts operationalized through survey research were

then compared to concepts of patient satisfaction operationalized with marketing or consumer research combined with an exploration of concept analyses to comprehensively define patient satisfaction for both patients receiving anesthesia care as well anesthesia providers wishing to improve the patient care experience.

The manuscript culminated with recommendations for anesthesia practice that may enhance patient satisfaction. Recommendations to improve PSAC went beyond quality improvement based on satisfaction survey results. They included conceptual changes that involve improving the patient experience with anesthesia care leading to increased patient perceptions of satisfaction. Recommendations targeted all anesthesia providers.

Ethics

Institutional review board approval was not sought. In this project, there was no patient contact. All findings and recommendations were based on previously published research or manuscripts.

Publication

The manuscript will be submitted to the *American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) Journal*. Manuscript submissions must include a title page with author's name and biography. Submissions will include key words, a 200-word abstract and manuscript in American Medical Association (AMA) style with references. All reproducible permissions will be included as well (American Association of Nurse Anesthetists, 2015). The *AANA Journal*, published bimonthly, offers scientific and clinical information aimed at advancing the practice of nurse anesthetists (American

Association of Nurse Anesthetists, 2015). *AANA Journal* readers include nurse anesthetists, educators, nurses and physicians (See Appendix B).

Evaluation

Evaluation of the final manuscript by doctoral committee members and two practicing nurse anesthetists will be determined in relation to whether it offers the following:

- adequate presentation of empirical evidence related to satisfaction with anesthesia care,
- a clear definition of patient satisfaction embedded within a useful framework for conceptualizing patient satisfaction,
- practical recommendations to anesthesia providers to improve patient perceptions of satisfaction, not only as a quality improvement or performance measure, but also as a method to enhance the patient experience with anesthesia care.

A successful manuscript will meet these criteria while adhering to *AANAJ* manuscript guidelines.

RESULTS: PROJECT MANUSCRIPT

The manuscript (Appendix A) will be submitted to the *American Association of Nurse Anesthetists Journal*. The *AANA Journal* guidelines for authors can be found at <http://www.aana.com/newsandjournal/Pages/aanajournalonline.aspx>.

CONCLUSIONS

Current Practice: Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care

Patient satisfaction with anesthesia care has traditionally been a desired goal as well as a measure of good care (e.g., determinant of care quality). While many nurse anesthetists understand the importance of having patients feel satisfied with their anesthesia care, few understand the complex process driving patient satisfaction. This process includes prior patient surgical/anesthetic experiences, patient expectations, provider interactions, and perceived quality outcomes, all of which are affected by patient emotions such as fear and anxiety. Complicating this further, published evidence documents multiple ways to measure patient satisfaction with anesthesia care. However, lack of a standard measure may also be partly due to the complexity of issues surrounding the surgical experience. Failure to understand patient satisfaction and its correlates may limit anesthesia providers' ability to positively impact patients' satisfaction with their care.

This integrative evidence review found support for the Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care Model, adapted from research completed outside of health care settings. This new model postulates that patients' expectations, values, and perceptions shape their satisfaction, and that patient beliefs about providers and provider performance also play a large role (see Figure 4) (Newsome & Wright, 1999; Oliver, 1993). Unique to this model is the addition of preoperative patient emotions serving as a starting point from which patients form expectations about their anesthesia experience.

While the qualitative evidence and research outside of healthcare supports the importance of patient emotions on satisfaction with a care experience, most published

studies focused on anesthesia care do not consider patient emotions (Costa, 2001; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; Hudson et al., 2015; McCloud et al. 2013; Newsome & Wright, 1999; Thompson & Sunol, 1995; Webster et al., 2011). In fact, only half of the eight studies that offered a conceptual definition of PSAC included patient emotions as a unique component of patient perceptions (Auquier et al., 2005; Baroudi et al., 2010; Capuzzo et al., 2005; Hawkins et al., 2014; Jjala et al., 2010; Myles et al., 2000; Schiff et al., 2008; Sindhvananda et al., 2003). However, all eight did consider patient expectations, perceptions, and outcomes as influential to PSAC (Auquier et al., 2005; Jjala et al., 2010; Schiff et al., 2008; Sindhvananda et al., 2003).

Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care Model

Figure 4. A model of anesthesia patient satisfaction that incorporates disconfirmation theory, a differentiation between actual and perceived service, and patient preoperative emotions.

Outstanding anesthesia care may enhance PSAC, but is not always a determinant of it. In fact, perceptions of high quality in the absence of actual high quality service can occur such as when a patient, in the absence of being seen or treated, recommends a provider to a friend (Newsome & Wright, 1999). Patients presented with a written anesthetic report during a visit from an anesthesia provider outlining the type of anesthesia given including procedures and medications were more satisfied with the quality of their anesthesia than patients receiving the same anesthesia care without the visit or report (Fleisher et al., 1999; LeMay et al., 2000). In addition, patient perceptions charged with intense and personal emotions may lead to a re-evaluation of prior feelings of dissatisfaction (Thompson & Sunol, 1995). Pain and nausea strongly predict patient dissatisfaction yet perceptions of satisfaction change at differing time points dependent on patient symptomatology (Royse et al., 2013). Patients who experience relief of severe pain may no longer focus on earlier feelings of dissatisfaction. Interestingly, post anesthesia patient satisfaction scores can even be unchanged in the event of unintended and untoward anesthetic events (LeMay et al., 2000).

Evidence from patient surgical experiences further underscores differences between patient satisfaction and care quality. Patients can be satisfied in the face of poor care, and dissatisfied upon receiving excellent care. This is problematic since patient satisfaction results are often used to assess quality. Evaluation of the evidence, however, elucidates and strengthens the heightened degree of the impact of peri-operative patient emotions as well as patient/provider relationships in determining patient perceptions of satisfaction or dissatisfaction (Costa, 2001; Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010; Hadjistavropoulos et al, 2001; Webster et al, 2011). Patients critique their care quality based on emotions

(McIlraith, 2015). Hudson et al. (2015) identified a theme of caring as instrumental to positive patient perceptions of satisfaction. Provider reassurance, good communication, and a balance between providing anesthetic information and listening can help to significantly reduce preoperative anxiety thereby improving patient satisfaction scores (Costa, 2001; Hudson et al., 2015; McCloud et al., 2013; Webster et al., 2011). The important message to providers is that patient emotions must be addressed in order to enhance patient satisfaction.

Implications for Anesthetist Practice: Enhancing Patient Satisfaction

Due to the financial incentives generated by positive patient satisfaction surveys, hospitals and anesthesia groups are compelled to consider patient satisfaction as a measure of care quality. What can anesthesia providers do? Surgery is often an emotionally charged experience for patients and anesthesia providers tend to approach patients from a cognitive perspective (McIlraith, 2015). The evidence from this review, however, suggests that in addition to providing excellent technical care, anesthetists need to engage emotionally with patients. They must listen to their concerns and fears, allay their preoperative anxiety, and carefully, answer patient questions (see Table 3). These actions show patients that anesthesia providers care.

Table 3

Modifiable Factors of Patient Satisfaction and Recommendations for Practice

Modifiable patient satisfaction domains	Potential action
Fear/anxiety	Emotionally engage with patients. Listen to patient fears/anxiety.
Information/risks and benefits explained	Set reasonable expectations. Address patient concerns and answer questions truthfully.
Answer questions	Emotionally engage with patients.
Pain/discomfort	Present reasonable expectations for pain/discomfort preoperatively.
Postoperative nausea and vomiting	Tell patients they will have postoperative discomfort. Promptly address and treat pain/discomfort/nausea.
Involvement in decision making	Include patients in discussion of anesthetic Offer choices when available.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Scarce evidence describing patient experiences with anesthesia was found.

Therefore, more qualitative research specific to these patient experiences with anesthesia care is needed; results would be insightful in furthering anesthesiologists' comprehension of these stressful patient experiences. Particularly needed is information about what patients expect and how they interpret care delivery by anesthesia providers.

Future development of a standardized valid and reliable patient satisfaction survey with anesthesia care is needed. Such a survey would measure dimensions that address the emotional component driving patient expectations and perceptions may offer a unified and more accurate approach to satisfaction measurement. In addition, simulation training for anesthesia providers that specifically addresses the highly anxious patient during anesthesia simulation or role play exercises may aid providers-in-training to effectively prepare patients for surgery.

The timely provision of patient satisfaction survey results to anesthesia providers may also be beneficial in effecting a practice change. Hocking et. al. (2013) discovered that feedback given to anesthesia providers did yield a change in practice. The post-feedback group of providers gave more antiemetic therapy to patients in the post anesthesia care unit (Hocking et al., 2013). When possible, a postoperative visit from the provider who delivered the anesthesia care may additionally benefit both the patient as well as the provider. Saal et al. (2011) claim that patients were more satisfied with their anesthesia care if they received a visit from an anesthesia provider following surgery. Such a visit additionally offers the provider direct insight into patient perceptions of anesthesia care.

According to the Institute of Medicine (as cited in McIlraith, 2015), satisfied patients are less likely to pursue litigation, have improved outcomes, and are more compliant with treatment. Improving patient satisfaction scores with anesthesia must reach beyond treating the results generated from survey measures, especially since HCAHPS scores, used for reimbursements, do not specifically address patient satisfaction with anesthesia. Improving patient satisfaction requires anesthesiologists to address and treat patients as whole persons. Using the Anesthesia Patient Satisfaction Model as a guide, anesthesiologists can intervene in patient care, address patient emotions, and influence patient perceptions at points that will achieve the greatest impact in improving patient satisfaction (see Figure 4).

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APPENDIX A

MANUSCRIPT SUBMITTED TO *AMERICAN ASSOCIATION OF NURSE ANESTHETISTS JOURNAL*

Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care – What Do We Know?

Nurse anesthetists provide anesthesia to thousands of surgical patients annually. Typically, upon patient delivery to the recovery room, anesthetists perform a cursory assessment of vital signs, physical status, and patient comfort before evaluating another patient and returning to the operating room. Due to rapid operating room turnover and short recovery room stays, insight into patient satisfaction with anesthetic care is often lost or not reliably evaluated. In most institutions, satisfaction with anesthesia care is included as part of the generic patient satisfaction surveys delivered to surgical patients one to three days post discharge. Anesthetists receive reports of patient dissatisfaction with anesthesia only in the event of negative feedback related to poor or catastrophic patient outcomes.

Much research related to patient satisfaction with anesthesia care (PSAC) documents satisfaction with post-operative physical outcomes (e.g., pain, nausea).¹ Patient satisfaction, however, also depends upon patients' thoughts, feelings, and values.¹ These factors are difficult to measure and may not be reflected in current practice indicators.

Current Context of Anesthesia Care. Interactions with patients prior to anesthesia can be done in ways which offer them a sense of personal control while relieving their anxiety and improving safety by providing opportunities for error reduction.² Perioperative communication as to presence of comorbid conditions, past

allergic reactions, surgical site markings, and potential postoperative complications aid in ensuring quality care, but also promotes patient trust with providers.²

Recently, in collaboration with the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ), the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) standardized patient satisfaction metrics. They recommend the use of two patient surveys: the Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (CAHPS) and Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS).³ Beginning in 2008, CMS has used survey results to calculate value-based payments. Since 2012, per the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act, survey results are used in determining incentive payments; HCAHPS scores are coupled with annual payment updates. When hospitals subjected to inpatient prospective payment systems fail to report these, they experience reductions in reimbursements.³ These payment trends suggest that patient satisfaction surveys could be used in calculating future anesthesia reimbursements.

Important to anesthesia providers, patient perspectives underpin the decision to pursue litigation.⁴ Specifically, positive patient-provider relationships prior, during and after surgery have been found to mitigate litigation.⁴ In an analysis of Press Ganey, satisfaction surveys from 1998 to 2006, providers that were rated as “very good” had no filed lawsuits (0% risk of litigation) in contrast to those rated as “very poor” with up to a 20% risk of litigation.⁴

What is Patient Satisfaction? Patient satisfaction is viewed as a comparison between patient expectations of a health-related experience and actual outcomes.¹ Hinging on patient values and perceptions, it is most often measured using surveys or interviews.¹ Given this, a definition of patient satisfaction should drive the specific

questions or items within any survey used. Valid and reliable survey development, thus, is based on concept clarity.⁵

An exploration of a concept analysis⁵ offers insight for a definition and clarification of patient satisfaction. Taxonomies of patient satisfaction with care include dimensions such as care thoroughness, giving/receiving information, and provider characteristics: courtesy, concern, respect and demeanor.⁵ Antecedents of satisfaction include social influences, patient characteristics, prior experiences with healthcare (e.g., surgery/anesthesia), environmental influences, cognitive status, and affective responses related to the care experience.⁵ Most descriptions of patient satisfaction with care delivery describe a link between patient satisfaction and expectations.⁵ That is, patients compare the actual care experience with a subjective standard or expectation. Consequently, expectations generate emotional responses which evolve from cognitive processes when comparing prior expectations to an actual experience.⁵

The disconfirmation theory, developed by Oliver, explores this link between patient satisfaction and expectations.⁶ Disconfirmation theory highlights an imbalance between consumer expectations of service and perceived performance. When a consumer does not experience what is expected, s/he feels dissatisfied. Perceived performance can be distinguished from actual or technical performance, especially when the consumer is not familiar with the service. This is often the case with anesthesia.⁷

Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care Model

Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care Model

Figure 1. This is a model of anesthesia patient satisfaction that incorporates disconfirmation theory; a differentiation between actual and perceived service and emotions that reflects the dynamic nature of satisfaction.

Based upon the disconfirmation model, the patient satisfaction with anesthesia care model (Figure 1) underscores the relationship between patient expectations with perceived service as part of an interdependent loop shaping perceptions of satisfaction. Additionally, the model takes into account prior patient experiences and provider influence. Inputs such as the type of surgery, previous anesthetic experiences, comorbid conditions, learning or literacy needs, and health care values are factors that shape the expectations that patients have prior to surgery. Importantly, emotional responses (i.e., patient preoperative emotions) act as a determinant in shaping patient expectations and consequently, satisfaction. Across the research using the disconfirmation theory, responses such as joy, interest, attention, and anger create positive or negative feelings, which shape perceptions of satisfaction.⁶

The PSAC model suggests that personal contact with providers is important in influencing patient satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Findings from Linder-Peltz reveal that while expectations, values and perceptions shape patient satisfaction with healthcare, patient beliefs about a provider and provider performance play an even larger role. ^{as cited in}

⁸ These findings highlight the importance of the anesthetists' knowledge of patient expectations as well as the importance of the preoperative evaluation in determining patient satisfaction. The dynamic feedback loop in the anesthesia satisfaction model establishes a framework that may aid anesthetists in identifying and influencing some modifiable factors related to satisfaction with anesthesia care.

The purpose of this integrative review of evidence was to examine published evidence about patient satisfaction as it relates to anesthesia care in order to:

1. Identify modifiable factors related to satisfaction with anesthesia care.
2. Integrate findings that will provide recommendations for anesthesia providers regarding PSAC.

History and Review of Literature

The literature search covered English language sources published from 1993 to 2015. Articles included those about PSAC; pediatric and obstetrical studies were excluded. Multiple online resources were searched: Pubmed®, Google Scholar, Cinahl, Business (EBSCO), ABI Inform Complete, and ScienceDirect®. Databases were searched for publications relevant to PSAC that included reports of survey and qualitative study findings, psychometric characteristics of survey tools, and select consumer satisfaction studies used to inform model generation. Additionally, reference lists were searched to find related articles. The following search terms were used in all

combinations: patient satisfaction, perioperative, surveys, questionnaires, anesthesia, anesthesia care, patient experience, healthcare, qualitative studies, consumer satisfaction, disconfirmation theory, customer satisfaction, and marketing theory. The search yielded 7 systematic reviews, 27 relevant quantitative studies, seven 7 qualitative studies, and 9 consumer satisfaction articles (used for concept clarification and framework development).

Systematic Reviews. The systematic reviews about patient satisfaction focused primarily on psychometric testing of measures, but revealed high levels of PSAC overall. Patients reported their satisfaction with anesthesia care from immediately after surgery to several months postoperatively using mail-back questionnaires, face-to-face interviews, phone interviews or a combination thereof.⁹⁻¹²

Cross-sectional surveys using a Likert response format formed the basis of most measures of PSAC. Few primary studies reviewed contained rigorous psychometric testing.⁹⁻¹⁵ Barnett et al.⁹ reviewed over 3000 articles with a patient satisfaction outcome and found only 71 that reported psychometric testing of the patient satisfaction measure. Specific to anesthesia care, Bell et al.,¹⁵ Le May et al.,¹¹ and Fung and Cohen¹² reported a high likelihood of measurement error across studies, limited psychometric testing, and no control for confounding variables.

Despite the reported lack of rigor in development of patient satisfaction measures, Hawkins et al.,¹⁴ and Chanthong et al.¹⁰ disclosed common factors (inputs) affecting patient satisfaction: information, pain, postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV), wait times, interpersonal skills of providers, privacy, safety, continuity of care, emergence, and awareness.¹¹

Individual Studies Measuring Patient Satisfaction. Across 27 studies, PSAC was reported to be high. Congruence between survey item dimensions and patient satisfaction were consistent with the anesthesia satisfaction model as well as review findings (see Table 1).¹⁶⁻³⁹ Patient satisfaction scores were higher when providers communicated risks, benefits, alternative anesthesia options and answered questions prior to patients receiving anesthesia. Similarly, patients were more likely to report higher levels of satisfaction when engaged and included by anesthesiologists in decision-making than when not included.^{16-19,22,26,27} Saal et al. (2011) documented that continuity of care (e.g., postoperative visit by the anesthesia provider caring for the patient) also increased PSAC scores.

The collective evidence supports postoperative nausea, vomiting, and pain as major contributors to decreased patient satisfaction scores. Other dissatisfiers include preoperative fear and anxiety, postoperative complications, lack of inclusion of patients in decision-making, age (younger), education (higher), gender (females), type of surgery, American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) I or II, preoperative wait times (longer), alcohol habits (non-drinkers), and experiencing awareness under anesthesia (see Table 1).^{16-21,23,26,32,35-37,39} Additionally, Hocking et al.,¹⁹ Royse et al.,²¹ Shiff et al.,²⁹ and Myles et al.³⁵ found that longer surgeries contributed to patient dissatisfaction (see Table 1).

Several researchers found that providing patients with information, conducting a thorough risk to benefit assessment, and including patients in preoperative decision-making enhanced patient satisfaction.^{16-20,22,25-27,30,31,33,34,36} However, Gurusamy et al.,¹³ in a Cochrane review of clinical trials of education in laparoscopy, found no clear evidence that patient education improved satisfaction.

Developed in an effort to create a standardized instrument to measure patient satisfaction, the commonly used HCAHPS Survey was meant to be useful for patients in all hospital settings and exhibited sound psychometric testing.³ However, items in the final version³ are not specific to anesthesia care. Each requires a dichotomous answer choice (yes/no) and reflects a patient's overall hospital experience (see final row in Table 2).

Table 1

Percentage of Studies Supporting Specific Dimensions (Modifiable and Non-Modifiable) Leading to Dissatisfaction with Anesthesia Care

Note. AC = anesthesia complications, ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists, IA = intraoperative awareness, IDM = involvement in decision making, PONV = postoperative nausea and vomiting, RBA = risks and benefits assessment.

Despite consistent findings, of the 27 studies with patient satisfaction survey results, only 14 disclosed reliability and validity information on measures.^{17-20,25,28-33,37-40} Of these, methods of reliability testing and validation differed. Surveys were developed using expert panels, patient interviews, literature searches, individual researchers, or

adapted from other questionnaires. Survey/interview questions varied greatly (see Table 2).

Data capture differed across studies as well. Patients might have been interviewed, received a mailed survey, or provided with a handout by anesthesia providers or other persons. Complicating this, the timing of survey administration or patient interview varied from immediately after surgery (often in the post-anesthesia care unit) to days, weeks, or months post-operation. Given that test-retest reliability of a measure is sensitive to time, these outcome measures may be compromised.

Table 2

Patient Satisfaction Survey Items Categorized by Domain

Domain	Questions
Pain Discomfort Perioperative physical needs	My pain control during and after surgery was adequate. ¹⁷
	After surgery I had unpleasant feelings like thirst, hunger, nausea, headache. ²⁰
	After receiving the anesthesia service, to what degree, were you afraid of pain because of the anesthetic? ²⁵
	To what degree, after the operation, did you feel afraid of pain? ³⁸
	To what degree did you, after the operation, have postoperative pain? ²⁸
	My reports of pain were acknowledged by the anesthesiologist. My pain was controlled in a satisfactory manner by the anesthesiologist. ⁴¹
	I experienced little or no immediate side effects like nausea, vomiting, pain, dizziness or sore throat. ³⁴
	I felt pain. ³⁷
	From HCAHPS: During this hospital stay, did you need medicine for pain? During this hospital stay, how often was your pain well controlled? During this hospital stay, how often did the hospital staff do everything they could to help you with your pain? ³

While useful as an outcome measure in research, well-developed or validated questionnaires are not frequently used in clinical settings.⁹ This applies to those specific to anesthesia care. This lack of precision in operationalizing PSAC results in equivocal findings.⁵

What do patients say? Studies exploring satisfaction with anesthesia include patient experiences with retinal eye surgery, hip or knee replacement surgery, general surgery, and experiences in the perioperative period. Patients in most studies expressed strong preoperative feelings of anxiety and fear.^{27,42-47} Patients undergoing general anesthesia paradoxically reported high anxiety when being given information and when not being given enough information.²⁷ Patients undergoing regional anesthesia showed decreased anxiety and increased satisfaction scores following a music intervention.⁴³ In addition, patients expressed anxiety and multiple fears regarding surgery, anesthesia, pain, being awake during surgery, feeling helpless, loss of control, death, and fear of being cut.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷ Past patient experiences influenced anxiety levels. For example, patients with positive prior experiences reported less and lower levels of anxiety.^{27,44,45}

Prior patient experience may impact patient anticipatory anxiety when they are considering general or regional anesthesia. In a study describing patient experiences of having both regional and general anesthesia for hip/knee surgery,⁴⁵ patients reported a preference for regional anesthesia if they had a prior negative experience with general anesthesia; however, overall, patients described greater fear and anxiety in anticipation of regional anesthesia. In addition, patients often preferred the anesthesia type recommended by the anesthetist or surgeon.⁴⁵

Across the qualitative studies, patients desired positive experiences with providers.^{27,42,45-47} Patients wanted to feel cared for and be known as a unique person throughout the perioperative period.⁴² Anesthesia providers who listened, were attentive, showed supportive behaviors, answered questions, and provided anesthesia information to their patients were able to emotionally connect with them; this emotional connection translated into patient satisfaction.^{27,42,46,47}

Current Practice: Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia Care

Patient satisfaction with anesthesia care has traditionally been a desired goal and a measure of good care (e.g., determinant of care quality). While many nurse anesthetists understand the importance of having patients feel satisfied with their anesthesia care, few understand the complex process driving patient satisfaction. This process includes prior patient surgical/anesthetic experiences, patient expectations, provider interactions, and perceived quality outcomes; all of these are affected by patient emotions (e.g., fear and anxiety). Complicating this further, published evidence documents multiple ways to measure PSAC. However, lack of a standard measure may also be partly due to the complexity of issues surrounding the surgical experience. Failure to understand patient satisfaction and its correlates may limit anesthesia providers' ability to positively impact patients' satisfaction with their care.

This integrative evidence review found support for the PSAC model, adapted from consumer research completed outside of health care settings. The model postulates that expectations, values, and perceptions shape patient satisfaction⁶ with patient beliefs about providers and provider performance playing a large role.⁸ In fact, perceptions of high quality in the absence of actual high quality service can occur such as when a

patient, in the absence of being seen or treated, recommends a provider to a friend.⁸ Patients presented with a written anesthetic report during a visit from an anesthesia provider outlining the type of anesthesia given, including procedures and medications, were more satisfied with the quality of their anesthesia than patients receiving the same anesthesia care without the visit or report.^{11,36} In addition, patient perceptions charged with intense and personal emotions may lead to a re-evaluation of prior feelings of dissatisfaction.⁴⁸ Pain and nausea strongly predicted patient dissatisfaction, yet perceptions of satisfaction changed at differing time points dependent on patient symptomatology.²¹ Patients who experience relief of severe pain may no longer focus on earlier feelings of dissatisfaction. Interestingly, post anesthesia patient satisfaction scores can even be unchanged in the event of unintended and untoward anesthetic events.¹¹

Evidence from patient surgical experiences further underscores differences between patient satisfaction and care quality. Patients can be satisfied in the face of poor care, and dissatisfied upon receiving excellent care. This is problematic since patient satisfaction results are often used to assess quality. Evaluation of the evidence, however, elucidates and strengthens the heightened impact of peri-operative patient emotions as well as patient/provider relationships in determining patient perceptions of satisfaction or dissatisfaction.^{27,42,45,47} Patients critique their care quality based on emotions.⁴⁹ Hudson et al.⁴² identified a theme of caring as instrumental to positive patient perceptions of satisfaction. Provider reassurance, good communication, and a balance between providing anesthetic information and listening can help to significantly reduce preoperative anxiety, thereby improving patient satisfaction scores.^{42,44,45,47} The important

message to anesthesia providers is that patient emotions must be addressed in order to enhance patient satisfaction.

While the qualitative evidence and research outside of healthcare supports the importance of patient emotions on satisfaction with a care experience,^{8,27,42,44,45,47,48} most survey studies focused on anesthesia care do not even consider patient emotions. In fact, only half of the eight studies that offered a conceptual definition of PSAC included patient emotions as a unique component of patient perceptions.^{17,26,29-31,35,38,40} However, all eight did consider patient perceptions and outcomes as influential to PSAC.^{29,30,38,40}

Implications for Anesthetist Practice: Enhancing Patient Satisfaction

Listed in Table 3 are potential mitigating actions for specific domains of PSAC.

Table 3

Modifiable Factors of Patient Satisfaction and Recommendations for Practice

Modifiable patient satisfaction domains	Potential action
Fear/anxiety	Emotionally engage with patients. Listen to patient fears/anxiety.
Information/risks and benefits explained Answer questions	Set reasonable expectations. Address patient concerns and answer questions truthfully. Emotionally engage with patients.
Pain/discomfort Postoperative nausea and vomiting	Present reasonable expectations for pain/discomfort preoperatively. Tell patients they will have postoperative discomfort. Promptly address and treat pain/discomfort/nausea.
Involvement in decision making	Include patients in discussion of anesthetic Offer choices when available.

Due to the financial incentives generated by positive patient satisfaction surveys, hospitals and anesthesia groups are compelled to consider patient satisfaction as a

measure of care quality. What can anesthesia providers do? While surgery is often an emotionally charged experience for patients, anesthesia providers tend to approach the patient from a cognitive perspective.⁴⁹ However, the evidence from this review supports that in addition to providing excellent technical care, anesthesiologists need to engage emotionally with patients. They must listen to their concerns and fears, allay their preoperative anxiety, and answer their questions (see Tables 1 and 3). These actions show patients that anesthesia providers care.

Future Considerations and Recommendations

Scarce evidence describing patient experiences with anesthesia was found. Therefore, more qualitative research specific to these patient experiences with anesthesia care is needed; results would be insightful in furthering anesthesiologists' comprehension of this stressful patient experience. Particularly needed is information about what patients expect and how they interpret care delivery by anesthesia providers.

Future development of a standardized valid and reliable patient satisfaction survey with anesthesia care is needed. Such a survey would measure dimensions that address the emotional component which drives patient expectations, perceptions, and satisfaction. In addition, it would offer a unified and more accurate approach to satisfaction measurement.

Another future consideration is implementing education/training for anesthesia providers that focus on effective communication skills with patients. This might be instituted through role play or simulation training. Scenarios could be constructed that specifically addresses the highly anxious preoperative patient and how positive rapport through communication and listening can be developed.

According to the Institute of Medicine (as cited in McIlraith, 2015), satisfied patients and are less likely to pursue litigation, have improved outcomes and are more compliant with treatment. Since the establishment of reimbursement is made primarily from patient surveys (CAHPS or HCAHPS) that lack inquiry regarding PSAC and do not equate to high quality anesthesia care, a false sense of satisfaction and quality of anesthesia care is reflected. Currently, there are no guidelines that are established for patient satisfaction and surveys that include anesthesia care. Therefore, anesthesia providers must be cognizant of treating patients as whole persons. In addition, by considering the PSAC Model as a guide, anesthesiologists can intervene in patient care, address patient emotions, and influence patient perceptions at points that will achieve the greatest impact in improving patient satisfaction.

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APPENDIX B
AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR JSDN

AANA Journal guidelines for manuscript submission must belong to the categories of research, review or survey, case report or other evidence-based project. Submissions in the category of other evidence-based projects must include work that advances the clinical, administrative or educational practice of nurse anesthetists. Any projects including animal or human study must hold to institutional review board (IRB) approval. Submissions must adhere to 12-point type and not exceed 20 pages of double-spaced text including figures, references and tables. A 50-reference maximum appearing in numerical order must be of previously published texts or articles.

Submissions must include a cover letter, title page, author information, keywords and abstract (200 word maximum), text, references, tables, figures, approvals (IRB) and any reproduction permissions. Figure legends, figures and tables may also be included. Tables must be double-spaced and submitted separately from figures.

APPENDIX C

TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Evidence Table 1. *Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia – Systematic Reviews*

Purpose (Source)	Design & Data Source	Study Selection & Sample	Data Extraction & Synthesis	Results or findings	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
CR of harms and benefits of preop education prior to lap chole surgery, includes analysis of preop education and PS (Gurusamy et al., 2014).	SR of 4 RCTs randomized to formal education compared to standard of care. 4 DBs searched.	Of the 431 pts who underwent an elective lap chole, 215 received formal preop education, 216 received SOC. 2 trials show effect of preop education on PS for total of 305 pts.	2 review authors ID'd the trials and collected the info using the <i>Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Intervention</i> . Extracted publication year, country, inclusion/exclusion criteria, details of preop education and outcomes. Synthesis via Review Manager 5 software – random effects and fixed effects. If a discrepancy, both are reported. Subgroup analysis of type of preop education and high vs low risk of bias.	Overall low quality of evidence and high potential for bias. Specific to PS: Quality of the evidence low. Formal education vs no education showed no difference in PS 95% CI 0.48(-0.42, 1.37).	Conclusions: Different RCTs with different outcomes obscuring accurate PS with formal education vs no education. No evidence that pt education benefits the pt. Limitations: Poor quality of evidence, impossible to blind pts as to whether they received education.
Systematic “qualitative” review of PS tools strengths and limitations (Barnett et al., 2013a)	SR of 71 articles referencing 34 PS tools.	All studies with questionnaire assessing PS with RA, LA, GA, MAC (ISAS), pediatrics (6 studies) and obstetrics (3 studies).	Two authors following meta-analysis standards, ID'd, searched & scored item generation, pilot testing, validity, reliability, & time to complete; highest score is 6. Extracted year, country, number of pts,	Not reporting obstetrics or peds. Limited tools for RA, lack of validation. ISAS for MAC cited in 17 studies. 5 studies scored a 6 (EVAN, EVAN-G, LeMay et al., Auquier et al., Shiff et al. & ISAS.	Conclusions: Of 3000 articles with PS as an outcome, 71 had psychometric development. ISAS – highest praise Capuzzo et al., & Bauer et al, suitable for QI measures. Limitations: Bias inherent in psychometric studies assessed. May have missed articles.

Purpose (Source)	Design & Data Source	Study Selection & Sample	Data Extraction & Synthesis	Results or findings	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
			dimensions, nature of items in dimension, response form, anesthesia, type of surgery, and results.	11 studies scored a 5 10 studies scored a 4 3 studies scored a 3 2 studies scored a 2. Overall PS reported as high.	No unified time or method for assessing PS. Note: High score for many articles?
IR of studies measuring PS with GA care; both descriptive and qualitative (R. Hawkins et al., 2012).	IR of 9 studies including PS with GA in adult pts from 3 DBs	9 studies measuring PS with GA: 6 descriptive, 1 prospective, 1 RCT, 1 qualitative and descriptive.	2 content experts evaluated on high/low, 2 point scale. Compared design, congruence of study with purpose & methodological rigor.	Of 9 studies: High rigor & relevance found in 3 studies, high relevance & low rigor in 2 studies, high rigor & low relevance in 3 studies, low rigor & relevance in 1. Modifiable factors predictive of PS in order: info, pain, wait times, provider interpersonal skills, PONV, attention, privacy, safe, well-being, premed, continuity, PACU care, emergence, treatment, awareness,	Conclusions: Relevance takes precedence over rigor. Limitations: Newest study 2008. Notes: Really helpful review.
SR of survey studies measuring PS in an ambulatory surgery setting (Chanthong et al., 2009)	SR of 11 primary studies from 7 DBs using and/or developing questionnaires to assess PS.	Studies measuring PS in ambulatory pts or included ambulatory pts (GA, RA, MAC, TIVA, LA).	English publications searched only. Abstracts reviewed by 3 authors. Studies assessed for item generation, validity, reliability, internal consistency, inter/intra-rater.	Of the 11 included studies: 4 studies describe item generation (2 with face-to-face interviews, 1 expert panel, 1 from patient discussion, 7 studies had no item generation discussion. 3 studies pilot tested, a final version was retested in all 3. 2 studies tested validity: CV & CoV in 1 study, CoV only in 1 study. 5 studies tested reliability: α in 4 studies, test-retest in 1 study. Dimensions found: info,	Conclusions: Further studies needed for instrument validation and reliability testing with \uparrow rigor. Limitations: Exclusion of other language articles other than English.

Purpose (Source)	Design & Data Source	Study Selection & Sample	Data Extraction & Synthesis	Results or findings	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
SR of instruments measuring PS with anesthesia and assessment of bias, and survey design (Bell et al., 2004).	SR of 5 studies from 5 DBs. Using PSACAT to evaluate survey design, timing of admin, length, response form, psychometrics, social desirability, nonresponse error, specificity of inclusion/exclusion, proxy use, incentives and confounders.	5 studies measuring PS in pts receiving anesthesia.	3 authors rated each of 5 studies using PSACAT which was developed and tested by authors with α 0.9. PSCAT = ME if survey given at least 15 min after surgery, finished in 5 min, with 50% RR, closed-ended, use of proxy or incentives, survey contained validity or reliability, and specific inclusion and exclusion criteria, confounders identified.	comfort, support, privacy, involvement, pain. In 5 studies: ME in survey design = 2 ME in timing = 2 ME in length = 2 ME in RR = 2 ME in psychometrics = 4 ME in social desirability = 2 ME in criteria = 2 ME in proxy = 3 ME in nonresponse = 2 ME in incentives = 0 ME in key variables = 4 ↑ ME across studies = ↓ ability to assess overall PS.	Conclusions: Large number of measurement errors in existing studies. Can use the PSACAT in individual setting to assess instrument measuring PS with anesthesia care. ISAS best psychometrics. Limitations: No discussion of types of anesthesia received in primary studies. Using tool developed by authors to assess primary articles. Notes: Confusing objectives.
Review all studies on PS specific to anesthesia (Le May et al., 2000).	SR of primary studies from 4 DBs on PS with anesthesia	Include PS with anesthesia care (ambulatory, hospitalized, GA, RA & MAC. 14 studies (4 RCTs, 10 convenience samples)	8 studies with no psychometric instrument eval. 3 studies used interviews, 6 used mail or handouts, 5 used combo of both. Only one study defined PS.	Most studies found ↑ levels of PS, only one researcher questioned this. Of 6 studies with psychometric eval, no control for confounders. All 6 psychometrically tested in different ways. No conceptual framework for any study.	Validity of all 14 studies questionable. In 4 studies, patients answered questions with anesthetist present. Test-retest reliability sensitive to time and not reliable when testing PS. Results may not accurately measure patient perceptions. Notes: Great review.
Review of methodology used to measure PS with anesthesia (D.	Review article including 20 primary articles from 1971-1997 in MEDLINE.	Studies include PS after GA with anesthesia care.	8 studies = mail back questionnaire 4 studies = face-to-face interviews 8 studies = telephone interview	80%-90% overall PS. Multi-item PS scales = > discrimination vs single-item. ↓ validity = ↓ generalizability. No reliability with PS	Conclusions: PS ↑ overall, but ↑ = gratitude, reluctance to criticize, tendency to report positives. Need for more psychometrics. Pt education regarding role of

Purpose (Source)	Design & Data Source	Study Selection & Sample	Data Extraction & Synthesis	Results or findings	Authors' Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Fung & Cohen, 1998).			No info on timing of postop info given.	measure across primary studies. Few studies to this point incorporate direct pt input. Better item generation = better instrument measuring PS.	anesthesia needed. Limitations: Older study, one database searched. No info given on how primary articles rated or reviewed. Confounders not discussed.

Note. Admin = administration, combo = combination, CR = Cochrane Review, CV = content validity, CoV = construct validity, DB = database, eval = evaluation, EVAN = evaluation du vécu de l'anesthésie , GA = general anesthesia, ID = identified, info = information, IR = integrative review, ISAS = Iowa Satisfaction in Anesthesia Scale, LA = local anesthesia, lap chole = laparoscopic cholecystectomy, MAC = monitored anesthesia care, ME = measurement error, min = minutes, PACU = post anesthesia care unit, PONV = postoperative nausea and vomiting, premed = premedications, preop = preoperative, PS = patient satisfaction, PSACAT = patient satisfaction with anesthesia care-analysis tool, QI = quality improvement, RA = regional anesthesia, RCT = randomized controlled trials, RR = response rate, SOC = standard of care, SR = systematic review, TIVA = total intravenous anesthesia, vs = versus.

Evidence Table 2. *Measures of Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia and Findings in Different Samples – Psychometric and Quantitative Studies*

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
PS with preop eval, RA and GA (Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014).	Design: Descriptive, cross sectional, survey. Key Variable: PS.	102 pts. Convenience sample, for elective surgery. Setting: University of Gondar teaching hospital, Ethiopia.	Patient satisfaction (PS): Level of PS with preop anesthetist visit. Questionnaire developed by researchers based on hospital anesthetic eval sheet. Results compared with Royal College of Anaesthetists' preop anesthetic eval standards.	Overall PS with preanesthetic visit 64.7%. PS comparison between receiving info and not receiving: type of anesthesia (72.7% vs 60.8%); anesthesia complications (85.7% vs 59.3%); postop analgesia (100% vs 57.1%); PONV (71.4% vs 62.9%); had questions answered (68.2% vs 58.3%); and 73% vs 50% PS with anxiety in pt receiving anesthetist visit.	Overall satisfaction ↓ compared with Royal College of Anaesthetists standards. Fear, PONV, and pain largest contributors to dissatisfaction. Limitations: No standardized preop eval, no questionnaire psychometric info, poor generalizability. Poor study quality but consistent outcomes.
Test content validity of items measuring PS with GA through ROL, (R. Hawkins et al., 2014)	Design: Psychometric testing. Key Variable: PS	13 CRNAs Setting: Uniformed Services University of Health Sciences as expert panel.	Primary provider theory used as conceptual framework. Content validity measured with expert panel using 4-point scale. Expert panel = providers with > 2 years providing GA.	Modifiable factors identified = info, pain, wait-time, anxiety, PONV, provider kindness, attention & concern. I-CVI scores > 8. S-CVI average = 0.98.	Items had high content validity. Next step to proceed with instrument development.
Pt involvement in preop decision-making regarding anesthesia (RA and GA) and effect on PS (Flierler, Nübling, Kasper	Design: Descriptive, cross sectional survey design. Key variable: PS.	186 pts Convenience sample of pts >16 years of age, ASA 1-3. Setting: St. Gallen, Switzerland.	PS = involvement in decision making between pts & anesthetists. Measurement: 2 questionnaires to pts & anesthetists eval congruence & involvement in decision-making. Questionnaire 1: validated	Overall PS 88%. Congruence between pt preference and anesthesia assumption, 54.1 (16.2) vs 56.4 (27.6), $p = 0.24$; congruence of perceptions of anesthesia decisions, 60(20) vs 42.4(27.4)*; degree of patient involvement in decision-making was not significant. Regression models	Conclusions: Most pts want inclusion in anesthesia decision-making preop, prefer a balanced decision-making model. Limitations: Selection bias of anesthetists as they chose to participate, Hawthorne effect; assessment of pt preference can change during anesthetist visit, limited generalizability; study

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
& Heidegger, 2013).			MAPPIN'SDM assess involvement with decision-making; 15 items omitted. Questionnaire 2: 4-category measure from very-satisfied to unsatisfied.	re PS with shared decision making shows highest PS scores in older pt** who have a ↑ level of decision making**; $F_{(2)} = 37.2^{**}$. ↓ PS when pts felt they contributed less*.	done in Switzerland, no psychometric scale information. Notes: Useful with regard to importance of providing info in the preop visit.
Development of questionnaire assessing anesthesia quality (RA and GA) from pt perspective (Hocking, Weightman, Smith, Gibbs & Sherrard, 2013).	Design: Quasi-experimental in 2 parts. Psychometric pilot study Part 2: Prospective longitudinal repeated measures QI study.	Part I: 714 pts PQA. Convenience sample for part I and part II. Setting: Part I, from authors' practice face-to face and e-mail interviews. Part II Sir Charles Gairdner Hospital	Psychometric questionnaire: Top 12 attributes included and developed from personal interviews. Questionnaire responses using Likert scale to the 12 items. Measurement: Quality Of health care Through the pts Eyes QuOTE series of studies. PS: Defined as patient-perception of quality of anesthesia care using PQA developed in part I.	Part I: Test-retest $r = .88^{**}$ for PQA test items such as gentleness, pain, information, confidence, concerns addressed and recommend anesthetist; adequate postop content validity with $r = 0.84^{**}$; medical expert content validity $r = 0.72^{**}$. Part II: Prior to anesthesia feedback: Unsatisfactory responses to >1 factors occurred in 47%, 95% CI [43.1, 47.4]; 12%, 95% CI [12.1, 14.0] were unsatisfied in >2 areas; 3.4%, 95% CI [2.7, 4.3] unsatisfied in >3 areas. Post-feedback group: 35%, 95% CI [32.6, 37.6] unsatisfactory performance in > 1 area; 5.6%, 95% CI [4.5, 6.9] unsatisfied > 2 areas and 0.9%, 95% CI [0.5, 1.6] unsatisfied > 3 areas.	Conclusions: Part I: Authors developed a tool to measure pt perceptions of anesthesia. Part II: Older males undergoing shorter procedures = ↑ PS. Limitations: No PA. Hawthorne Demographics different between groups. Notes: Study difficult to read. May have been easier if published as two separate studies. Many good tables! The post-feedback group had higher occurrence of antiemetic therapy.
Development and validation of questionnaire that assesses PS in RA only (Maurice-	Design: Descriptive, cross sectional survey design. Key variables:	390 pts : 238 from a prior study, convenience sample. 152 pts given regional	PS: assessed related to pain, fear, anxiety, and questions answered with RA using EVAN-LR. Psychometric test: EVAN-LR developed from the	PS: Women ↓ in info dimension. ASA I and II pts ↓ in attention dimensions. Older pts ↑ satisfied in all dimensions except attention. Psychometrics: Correlation between items and dimensions ↑,	Conclusions: Good communication improves PS. First RA questionnaire assessing PS. Free-form interviews from original qualitative study. Confounding anxiety addressed

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
Szamburski, Bruder, Loundou, Capdevilia & Auquier, 2013).	Psychometric questionnaire (EVAN-LR) validation, PS.	anesthesia. Setting: Three university hospitals in Southeast France.	results of qualitative study. Internal and external validity measured with question matching and comparison with other PS instruments	0.30 to 0.75. Correlation between items and other dimensions ↓ confirming high discrimination among items. Cronbach α .60 - 0.88. Correlations between EVAN-LR and APAIS, STAI state, and VAS low; EVAN-LR does not measure same items as other tests. APAIS and discomfort, $r = -.316^*$; STAI and pain, $r = .219^*$; VAS and consideration as person and attention, $r = .224^*$; VAS confidence in staff and waiting, $r = .306^*$.	through correlation with the APAIS. Scale validity and reliability determined. Limitations: Generalizability questionable due to location of France, however, RA remains standardized. Inclusion of pts from pilot study with new pts using a shorter version of scale may alter results. Notes: Only study addressing RA.
Purpose to assess predictors of PS and anesthesia using a validated scale (PQRS) with GA cases only, (Royse, Chung, Newman, Stygall & Wilkinson, 2013).	Design: Descriptive secondary analysis of an observational cohort study. Key variables: PS, PQRS.	701 pts, dataset from prior study using convenience sampling. Setting: Melbourne, Australia at the University of Melbourne.	PQRS: PQRS measures 5 domains (physiological, nociceptive, emotive, ADLs, and cognitive recovery) with overall perspective as 6th domain; measured at 15 minutes, 40 minutes, 1-3 days and 3 months postop. PS: Single question about PS with anesthesia, 5-point response. Not satisfied = any response other than "totally satisfied".	PS and PQRS: 17% expressed some dissatisfaction at postop day three predicted by pain and nausea, OR = 8.2, 95% CI (2.5, 27)*. Other variables predicting dissatisfaction at day three include: ↓ weekly alcohol intake**, ex-smoker ($p = .022$), increased time under anesthesia**, inpatient status**, major surgery*, premedications ($p < .001$), history of depression*, and anxiety*. MLR, 52% variance in PS accounted for. 4 independent predictors: pain and PONV day 3, OR = 8.2, 95% CI [2.5, 27]*; dissatisfaction day 1, OR = 28, 95% CI [10-77]*;	Conclusions: High proportions of pts totally satisfied with anesthesia at day 3. ↓ PS predicted by PONV and pain at day 1, while early pain and PONV on day 1, T ₁₅ predicted ↑ PS. Limitations: Only one question asking if the patient is satisfied overall (5 point Likert scale); wide variety surgical procedures, but different cohorts may experience different outcomes; wide age range may be considered a confounding variable; and difficult to assess PS in children. Notes: Well formulated study.

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
				pain or PONV T ₁₅ , OR = .34, 95% CI [.11, .99]*; and day 1, OR = .31, 95% CI [.10, .91]*.	
PS with verbal preop anesthesia info (RBAs) (Puro et al., 2013).	Design: Descriptive, cross sectional, survey design. Key variables: PS, Preop anesthesia info.	372 subjects and their APs (24) from OBGYN hospital in Helsinki and Uusimaa, Finland. Subjects had hysterectomy between 9/2007 and 12/2008.	PS: Measured by 2 page Likert-type questionnaire assessing PS about comprehensiveness of preop interview and RBAs. Questionnaire based on law and DISCERN. Questionnaire to AP same with added question about typical pt info practice. DISCERN: instrument to eval quality of info on treatment choices.	82% PS with amount of preop info; 93% APs felt they provided adequate info. 74% PS with info about RBAs. 60% of APs provide RBAs. 62% PS with discussion of alternative anesthetics; 60% of APs provide alternative choices. 49% PS with discussion on quality of life; 27% APs provide quality of life info. 93% pts wish info to be given by provider, 68% written info, 18% independent provider, 16% other pt experiences. Overall 25% pts felt they received inadequate info.	Conclusions: APs overestimate what pts know about anesthesia. Not enough info being given about RBAs, self-help interventions & quality of life. Need to provide pts more info about anesthesia. Verbal info from AP the most preferred method. Written info may aid in pt recall of info. Limitations: Low response rates (48%), only females from Finland undergoing scheduled hysterectomy.
PS with GI endoscopic procedures in Iranians under GA (S. Iravani et al., 2012).	Design: Prospective survey design. Key Variables: PS, GA, colonoscopy, endoscopy	756 subjects from 4 hospitals in Tehran, Iran. 2 groups, not randomized.	PS: Measured by 7 point Likert scale developed by researchers, validated on 30 subjects. G1 received GA, G2 did not.	51.5% received GA. 59% female All subjects from urban area. ↑ education level = ↑ PS**. Total satisfaction ↑ with GA**.	Conclusions: Improved PS with ↑ education and GA. Limitations: Did not operationalize GA, little information regarding scale validation, all subjects from urban area, no randomization. Notes: Poor study quality.
Purpose to assess influence of type of anesthesia & gender on anxiety, GA, LA, RA	Design: Descriptive cross sectional survey. Key Variables: Anxiety	Convenience sample of 674 returned questionnaires. Setting: Day surgery in	Questionnaire for GA 59 items, for RA/LA 61 items with Likert scale format. Questionnaire developed via expert panel and literature. CV established with expert panel.	82.4% pts with anxiety, 34% remained anxious after surgery 24-48 hours. Highest anxiety provoking aspects: waiting, pain anticipation, unknown. Type of anesthesia on variables**: anxiety on day of	Conclusions: Pts desired more info. Anxiety related to unknown common. Contact with staff and info helps. Pts preferred info 1-4 weeks prior to surgery. Female pts preferred to spend time with family/friends

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
(Mitchell, 2011).		Manchester, UK.		surgery, anxiety first start, written info. Anxiety ↑ with GA vs LA or RA. Gender on variables**: anxiety on day of surgery, anxiety start, info, unit aesthetics, talking to other pts, reading info, music, friend with pt. Female with ↑ anxiety.	prior to surgery. Limitations: Little info on scale development. More females than males surveyed. Notes: One author? Why not use established anxiety scale? Questions provided.
Development of PSPACq and psychometric validation for GA, RA and MAC (Mui et al., 2011).	Psychometric questionnaire (PSPACq) validation of PS with anesthesia care.	Part I pilot (G1 = 320 subjects, GA only) Part II PSPACq validation (G2 = 565 subjects GA, G3 = 225 RA subjects) Part III: Nomologic validation. Setting: Christian hospital in Taiwan.	6-factor, 32 item survey developed from prior study. Part I: Exploratory factor analysis in 5 dimensions: info, discomfort and needs, relationships, fear, wait times. Validity coefficient and homogeneity reliability coefficient used to evaluate content. Part II: Confirmatory factor analysis. Questionnaire given 6-48 h after GA or RA. Part III: Construct relationships compared with similar constructs	Part I: V and H coefficient show significance in individual items and questionnaire**. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin sampling measure 0.80** indicating appropriate factor structure. Factor analysis resulted in deletion of 2 items. All remaining $\alpha > .70$. Part II: Confirmatory analysis with G2 on RA and GA show fit index > 0.90 ** for an acceptable survey, $\alpha > .70$. Part III: Scores influenced by age, sex, education, type of anesthesia and surgery type. Older men with lower educational levels receiving GA are more satisfied. Overall PS not reported.	Conclusions: Final survey 30 items, 7 factors testing PS in Taiwanese patients. The questionnaire from Heidegger et al., EVAN-LR and GA, ISAS and Leiden scales used for comparison. Limitations: V & H coefficients described in prior study. Limited generalizability due to Taiwanese patients only. Notes: Some qualitative info reported. Difficult to sift through.
I postop visit and effect on PS with GA and RA, (Saal, Heidegger, Nuebling & Germann, 2011).	Design: Randomized prospective study design. DV: Continuity of care and PS in 5 dimensions.	642 subjects Block random assignment into 3 groups on 1 st postop day. Setting: Tertiary hospital,	PS: Continuity of care equals PS and defined as 1 anesthetist for preop, intraop anesthesia and postop visit. Measure: Questionnaire assessing dimensions of decision-making	No postop visit problem score of 13.5%, 95% CI [\pm 6.9], in G1; 69.2%, 95% CI [\pm 10.3] in G2; 77.1%, 95% CI [\pm 9.1] G3. G1 vs G2 and G1 vs G3**. Continuity of care problems scores 40%, 95% CI [\pm 5.3] in G1; 48%, 95% CI [\pm 5.6] in G2; and	Conclusions: A postop visit from the anesthesia provider ↑ pt's perception of continuity of care and PS. ASA III or ↑, males, outpatients ↑ PS. Limitations: Study done in Austria; role of CRNA different,

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
	IV: G1=visit with anesthetist in case, G2=visit by nurse anesthetist not in case, G3=no visit	Feldkirch Austria. PA done, power of >.8 = 200 per G.	involvement, confidence, waits or delays, PACU nursing, pain, and continuity. Measured negative pt response or problem score. Continuity and overall dissatisfaction = total problem score. Data retrieved after single visit by same anesthetist, nurse anesthetist, no visit.	55.5%, 95% CI [\pm 5.3] in G3, between G1 and G3**. ASA III pts (6.3%, 95% CI [\pm 5.2]) \uparrow dissatisfaction than ASA I and II*; university vs high school (7.2%, 95% CI [\pm 4.0]**). Males and outpatients, \downarrow problem score in all groups*. Importance of a postop visit \uparrow G1**.	limited generalizability due to cultural and education differences. Notes: Authors claim that \uparrow PS if they receive a visit from a CRNA when they expect an MD, but study results do not support this. Well-executed study.
Purpose to validate the modified ISAS for Arabic speaking pts and assess PS, GA and RA, (Baroudi, Nofal & Ahmad, 2010).	Design: Descriptive, cross sectional, survey design. Key variables: PS.	803 pts convenience sample. Setting: M.S. Barsharahil Hospital, Saudia Arabia.	PS: The original ISAS, translated into Arabic and modified to reflect the Arabic culture. Questionnaire dimensions measured: info, decision-making, accessibility of anesthesiologist, respect from nurses, PACU care, fear and anxiety.	PS: Dissatisfied pts were primarily women (58%), ASA I and II (73%) and college educated (55%)*. Dimensions contributing to \downarrow PS are: info, decision-making and PACU care.	Conclusions: \uparrow PS scores if pain and anxiety controlled, PS \uparrow with \uparrow info, and good PACU care. Limitations: Study done in Saudi Arabia, but providing culturally appropriate care makes study minimally generalizable to US, Hawthorne effect, tables with limited value minimal reported data. Notes: Personal bias reported.
Purpose to assess PS with general and urology surgery preop, GA only, (Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010).	Design: Cross sectional, survey design. Has qualitative component Key variables: PS	275 pts day surgery under GA from Bristol Community Health, Lawrence Weston Clinic, United Kingdom	PS: Measured by questionnaire developed by researchers through qualitative study and piloted. Open-ended questions included. Themes: preop info, support, and anxiety.	PS: \uparrow PS with \uparrow communication. Reported from results of open-ended questions.	Conclusions: \uparrow PS through nurse-led preop assessment providing good communication & addressing anxiety. Limitations: Much qualitative data (see qualitative TOE). No psychometric testing. Not anesthesia specific. Notes: Good qualitative data. No statistics for results.
Purpose to validate an	Design: Psychometric	100 pts receiving GA or	LPPSq translated from Dutch to English and	Validity, reliability and factor analysis performed: $\alpha = 0.56-0.89$	Conclusions: Good reliability, but low reliability in discomfort.

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
English LPPSq with ortho pts and assess PS in GA, RA and GA & RA combo (Jlala et al., 2010)	validation of translated & adapted LPPSq assessing PS	RA or combo for ortho surgery in Queens Med Ctr, United Kingdom	extended to include anesthesia side-effects and info about anesthesia: Total 39 questions. Dimensions measured: Info, discomfort, fear, staff/pt relationship, competence, service. Pts asked to complete within 3 days.	for inter-item correlation, discriminant validity low (0.01-0.37) = weak correlation of items with other dimensions. PS mean = 86.7%. Age, gender and surgery type not a PS influence. HA ↑ in RA vs GA (46% vs 12%)* ↑PS with staff dealing with complaints (89%), competence (76%). RA ↑ PS than GA.	Added items did not change the PS measurement. PS ↑ overall. Providers give more info for RA procedures & pts like this. PS not affected by type of anesthesia. RA pts ↑ PS than GA. Limitations: No info regarding extended questionnaire material. One translator only. Did not account for confounders. Notes: Questions included. Inconsistent results.
Purpose to validate & test reliability of LPPSq and assess PS; RA, GA and combo RA and GA (Caljouw et al., 2008).	Design: Psychometric questionnaire development and validation assessing PS	307 pts from the Netherlands with a wide variety of surgical cases recruited from a preoperative anesthesia unit.	PS: Part 1: Questionnaire development by expanding EVAN to include including additional elements such as provider/pt relationships, competence, service and information. Expert panel of 6 to eval EVAN. Pilot test with EVAN on 50 pts who were asked what was missing. Findings compiled to form LPPSq. PS: Part 2: Validity via factor analysis. Reliability via correlation between dimensions and items.	LPPSq - 39 questions (5-point Likert scale). Reliability: α (0.69-0.94) for item correlation & dimensions. α (0.53-0.83) for inter-item correlation. Items with ↓ correlations deleted. Validity: Factor analysis = 3 factors (60% variance) for PS: info (4 items), provider/pt relationship (13 items), fear (4 items). PS overall 92.1% Pain > in GA vs RA**. Cold > in longer surgeries* OR rated ↑ PS if pt/provider relationships ↑. Young, employed women ↓ PS.	Conclusions: Developed questionnaire that addresses info, pain, fear and relationships. Interactions between pts/providers influences PS. Pain influenced by gender, age, surgery, anxiety. Quality perceived by degree of support during hospitalization. Limitations: Confounders not addressed. Timing of questionnaire not discussed. Notes: Test questions provided
Purpose to develop, test and validate a peri-anesthetic	Design: Psychometric questionnaire development,	1398 pts and 59 HCWs from 3 teaching hospitals in	PS: Part I: Item generation and reduction. Semi-structured G interviews, expert panel	Part I: Items found via focus groups, interviews and literature search yielding 60 questions rated. Final version = 41	Conclusions: Validation of questionnaire at 3 different hospitals. Discomfort and emotional factors ↓ PS.

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
pt dissatisfaction questionnaire, GA or RA (Schiff et al., 2008).	testing and validation of pt dissatisfaction.	Germany.	ranked items, items made into questions with 4-pt Likert scale. Part II: Psychometric testing. Factor analysis for dimensions. Discriminant (items with dimensions), external (scores with VAS, STAI & APAIS), content validity & reliability (item/dimensions) tested. Univariate analysis for confounders.	questions. Part II: Factor analysis = 5 dimensions (trust, fear, discomfort, treatment by staff, information & waiting). Tx by anesthesia & VAS (r = 0.47*), tx by anesthesia & APAIS and STAI (r = 0.6*). $\alpha = 0.42 - 0.79$ between items and dimensions. \uparrow PS = \uparrow age**, \downarrow education**, shorter surgery**. Dissatisfaction associated with discomfort, thirst, fear, poor sleep, anxiety and long waits.	Limitations: Types of cases not discussed. Timing of questionnaire not discussed. Questionnaire given to pts receiving RA, but not designed for this.
Purpose to validate EVAN-G to assess PS in GA only (Auquier et al., 2005).	Design: Psychometric questionnaire development and validation of PS.	874 pts from 4 university hospitals in France in wide variety of surgical procedures.	PS: Part 1: Item generation from face-to-face interviews (semi-structured) yielding 75 questions from 3-person content analysis. 66-items in pilot study. Part 2: Validity and reliability assessed (correlations with dimensions and scales – MGPO, STAI, VAS) & expert panel. EVAN-G = 26 item scale. Dimensions: attention, pain, privacy, info, discomfort and waiting.	Scale 0-100 with 100 indicating \uparrow PS. Overall PS not reported, due to no PS standardization, items and dimensions only. Correlations between item and dimension (internal consistency) between 0.55-0.92. Convergent validity (EVAN-G and other scales)* \uparrow PS in older pts with minor surgery receiving an LMA vs ETT. Info \uparrow in premed G. Pain \uparrow in ASA >II, minor surgery, LMA. Waiting \uparrow in age > 65 and ASA > II. Cronbach α 0.73-0.91.	Conclusions: Scale reliable, valid and can be used in all anesthesia practice. Developed from patient and clinician views. To be given within 48 hours of surgery. Limitations: Not to be used for RA or MAC. Did not address confounders. Note: Well formulated study. Address importance of discovering patient dissatisfiers.

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
Purpose to validate questionnaire measuring PS with GA (Capuzzo et al., 2005).	Design: Psychometric questionnaire development, pilot, validation and test.	Pilot = 100 pts interviewed regarding items and asked to rank them. 219 pts interviewed with questions, answers on 0-10 scale, in Italy.	Part I: Expert panel selected 23 items. Interviewed pts asked to rate items of value s/p anesthesia in order of importance from 0-600. Part II: 10 items selected from part I. Pts interviewed, asked to rate on 0-10 scale (0 =no PS). Validation = comparing measurements and logical relationships. Reliability = test-retest.	Part I: Resulted in 10 items encompassing physical, emotional and relational concepts. Part II: Mean PS = 90.5. PS correlates with kindness, information and PONV ($r \geq 0.6$). No association with anxiety & PS. PS association with fear, attention & relaxed = 54% of variance. $\alpha = 0.84$. Inter-observer reliability (time between = 1 day).	Conclusions: Pts value elements emotionally & relational. Pts value info and communication more than physical elements. Questionnaire based on relevance to pts. PS ↑ overall. Limitations: Does not address confounders. Interviews may create bias. Vague dimensions. Validated in inpatients only, public insurance Notes: Lots of supposition.
Purpose to eval a website prior to surgery for impact on pt education, anxiety, & PS with anesthesia, GA only (Hering et al., 2005).	Design: Pilot study – prospective, experimental. Preoperative evaluation tool development to measure PS with anesthesia.	65 pts, ASA I, II for GA at Urban university hospital in mid Atlantic area. G1 = EG (n = 25) G2 = CG (n = 39).	Preoperative evaluation tool measuring PS with anesthesia Anesthesia info measured by mSALT. Anxiety measured by STAI. G1 given website instructional module. G1 & G2 given verbal info regarding anesthesia. STAI, mSALT and survey completed on day of surgery prior to surgery.	No differences in mSALT or STAI scores between groups. No differences within groups on STAI. G1 showed ↑ in mSALT scores within groups* - website group = ↑ info regarding anesthesia. Overall PS scores showed no differences between groups.	Conclusions: Website intervention did not improve anxiety or PS, but did improve perception of anesthesia info. Limitations: Expert panel tool development not discussed, reported as valid. 30 minutes to complete testing preoperatively. Anxiety level may influence ability to receive info.
Purpose to validate CEA – EQ and LA – EQ and assess PS in carotid endarterectomy pts, GA and LA,	Study in 2 parts: Part I: Qualitative: Open interviews to determine themes.	Part I: 130 pts, 20 interviewed to develop initial draft. 20 pts received first draft and interviewed.	Part I: CEA-EQ total of 28 items measuring 3 domains: anxiety, recovery and PS on 0-100 scale, lower score = better experience. Part II: 88 pts in G1, 88 in	Part I: Validated CEA-EQ with STAI-S, SSSQ. CEA-EQ correlated with SSSQ ($r = 0.41^{**}$), and STAI-S ($r = 0.60^{**}$). Item correlation 0.34-0.78*. Part II: No statistical differences	Conclusions: Positive experience with carotid endarterectomy regardless of anesthesia choice. Limitations: Part I: Limited domains. No patient experiences

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
(McCarthy et al., 2004).	Part II: Quantitative: Prospective randomized. PS: Using scale developed from part I.	Pilot test with remaining 90 pts Part II: 176 pts from Royal United Hospital Bath, prospective randomization. GA (G1)/RA (G2).	G2. Measuring three domains: anxiety, PS and recovery. Anxiety: hospital admission, LOS, fear. Satisfaction: length of wait, surgery, LOS, info, return to normal	between anxiety and PS in both groups. ↓ anxiety = ↑ PS Recovery score ↑ for G2*. Overall PS reported as ↑ regardless of anesthesia type.	recorded, no setting for interviews described. Part II: Limited generalizability, selection bias due to non-randomization, limited information about LA-EQ, cannot offer direct comparison. Notes: Good study Pts receiving LA felt more reassured if AP talked to pt during procedure.
Purpose to develop and validate PS with GA in Thai pts (Sindhvananda et al., 2003).	Design: Psychometric questionnaire development and validation of PS in Thai pts.	Items generated from lit review (including customer satisfaction), interviews from 30 pts. Questionnaire with 10 questions (5-pt Likert response). Thailand.	Item generation based on lit review and interviews for pilot study (n = 135), total 13 items. Pts interviewed 24-48 postop. Dimensions: Preop – fear of not waking, injections, loss of control, ↓ knowledge; Postop – shivering, pain, PONV. Final questionnaire = 10 items (n = 211).	Overall PS ↑ Content validity – item correlation with expert panel where scores ≥ 0.5 = valid. Reliability – α 0.90 and repeated at 0.76. Results of PS not reported	Conclusions: Questionnaire demonstrated validity and reliability. Limitations: Limited global generalization. Notes: Only study that included customer satisfaction. Difficult to understand, translated?
Purpose to assess PS and differences between survey vs face-to-face interviews (assume all anesthesia types) (Bauer et al., 2001)	Design: Randomized prospective. DV = PS IVs = questionnaire vs face-to-face interviews. Psychometric questionnaire	700 pts randomized to CG or EP completing interview or questionnaire on postop day 2. Setting: University	Questionnaire measuring PS includes 15 questions, 10 on discomfort (dichotomous), 5 subjective PS with anesthesia (4 item Likert). EG = interview CG = questionnaire	Reliability test-retest. IC: α = 0.84 CV measured with expert panel. 80% pts – drowsy, 40% pts with moderate discomfort or more, >50% pts thirsty, 25% PONV, 25% felt cold. Differences between written questionnaire and interview: Pain*, thirst*, drowsiness**.	Conclusions: Valid and reliable tool developed from expert panel? High level of PS overall consistent, but methodological issue. Interviews yielded more criticism and may be more valuable. Better to assess dissatisfaction.

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
	development for both grps.	hospital in Heidelberg, Germany		Info: EG = 54% PS, CG 77% PS** Discomfort: EG = PS 93%, CG PS 95% PS. PONV: EG = 80% PS, CG = 95% PS* Overall PS: EG = 98%, CG 98%, but questionnaire = 74% very satisfied, 24% satisfied; interview = 43% very satisfied, 55% satisfied.	Limitations: Little information on tool development. Types of surgeries listed but not types of anesthesia. Notes: Time factor consistent.
Purpose to assess pt perceptions of anesthesia care with info, involvement, comfort and emotional support; GA, RA, MAC (Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001).	Design: Descriptive cross sectional survey. Key variables: WCCS	268 pts sent mail-back WCCS. Setting: Saskatchewan, Canada.	WCCS measures dimensions of: info, provider involvement, respect, community transition, emotional support, and comfort. 5 pt Likert scale.	1018 sent, 268 surveys completed ANOVA shows pts rate dimension of comfort higher than info, involvement and emotional support. MANCOVA shows care uniform despite type of anesthesia, provider, or surgery type.	Conclusions: Pts felt positive about respect. Lower rates given to info, involvement and emotional support. Limitations: Limited reporting of statistics. Notes: Done from patient-centered approach. Questions provided. Difficult to read, translated?
Assess PS in outpatients via ranking of value and if APs could predict what pts ranked, unknown anesthesia type, GA? (D. Fung & Cohen, 2001).	Design: Descriptive cross sectional survey. Key Variables: 36-item questionnaire measuring PS.	Responses from 30 outpatients and 15 Aps. Setting: Toronto University Hospital, and community hospital, Toronto, Canada.	Questionnaire developed from telephone interviews. 4 time phases: preop, intraoperative, pre and post discharge. Dimensions: physical, technical content, interpersonal relationship, efficiency, outcomes. Pts and APs asked to rank items in each time phase Rank 1 = score 3 Rank 2 = score 2	Highest ranked items by patients related to communication and info. Physical conditions ranked low. Interpersonal trust ranked 2 nd in intraop time phase. Efficiency and outcome ranked highest in postop time phase. APs could not predict pt response. Pts want more info about side effects and care, APs emphasize friendliness. Inconsistency in pt	Conclusions: Pts value communication and information. Pts place least value on physical environment. APs cannot predict what pts value. Interpret ranking with caution. Limitations: Small convenience sample. Notes: Type of anesthesia not stated. Questions provided. Interesting that APs can't predict

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
			Rank 3 = score 1	responses: all items ranked highest by at least 2 pts.	what pts want so why do we have expert panel?
Purpose to assess modifiable factors affecting PS, GA and RA, (Myles, Williams, Hendrata, Anderson & Weeks, 2000).	Design: Descriptive, prospective design. Key variables: PS, PONV, pain and complications. Covariates: Age, ASA, smoking, sex, use of NMBAs, duration of anesthesia.	17,106 pts from chart audit of all pts receiving an anesthesia eval at 24 hours postop. Setting: Alfred Hospital in Melbourne, Australia.	PS: Defined by Likert-type scale. PONV and pain: Dichotomized. Postop complications = PONV, HA, sore throat, soft-tissue injury, MI, neurological deficits, back pain, muscle pain, urinary retention and confusion. Measurement: Results of formal interviews conducted by QA coordinator to assess PS.	There were 0.9% dissatisfied pts and 2.3% somewhat satisfied pts. Of these less satisfied pts, 3.2%, were younger** and had ↓ duration of anesthesia ($p = .018$). Findings in PACU odds ratio with 95% CI for dissatisfaction; adverse events 1.92 [1.47, 2.56]**; pain 6.95 [5.18, 9.33]**; PONV 2.85 [1.11, 7.34], $p = .02$. Findings 24 hours postop 95% CI; pain 3.94 [3.16-4.91]**; PONV 4.09 [3.18, 5.25]**; awareness 54.9 [1507, 191]**; complications 2.04 [1.64, 2.56]**.	Conclusions: Satisfied pts tended to be older males, ASA III or ↑. Dissatisfied pts were younger females, ASA I and II with ↓ durations of anesthesia. Postop complications, pain, PONV, awareness were also associated with ↓ PS. Limitations: Study done in Australia, no standardized interview process reported, reporting bias in that ASA III or IV pts may not be able to report accurately. Notes: Well-executed study. Results consistent with other studies.
Purpose to assess if ACR increases satisfaction, GA and MAC.(Fleisher et al., 1999).	Design: Randomized cross sectional. ACR = provides info regarding anesthesia care including blade, technique, meds	372 patients randomized from John Hopkins Hospital. MD to group receiving ACR and discharge info (G1) and group with regular discharge info only (G2).	PS: Measured using questionnaire with 7 item Likert scale developed from ophthalmologic clinic. Questionnaire mailed and via telephone.	G1 show ↑ PS with pain*. G1 show ↑ PS with perception of quality of care**. G1 showed ↑ PS from G2 (83% vs 67%).	Conclusions: Info given regarding anesthesia care increases PS. Limitations: No psychometric testing regarding survey, 61% survey response rate, limited generalizability due to lack of intraoperative complications, no information regarding type of surgery given.
ISAS development, with MAC	Design: Descriptive, cross sectional	Scale development 61 pts,	ISAS: Scale developed by expert panel of anesthesia providers with pt	Good internal consistency, $\alpha = .80$. Validity showed + correlation	Conclusions: Good internal consistency. + correlation with 2 other PS

Purpose (Source)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures, Definitions of Variables	Results	Author Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
(Dexter, Aker & Wright, 1997).	survey design. Key variables: ISAS measuring PS with MAC.	psychometric testing 87 pts. Setting: University of Iowa in Iowa City, Iowa.	participation. Scale = 11 statements using Likert scale. Statements composed by MDAs, CRNAs, SRNAs, residents, experts in questionnaire development, surgeons, OR and PACU nurses and administrators after a literature review. 1 question = 1 construct.	between scores predicted by anesthesia provider and pt scores ($r^2 = .23^*$). PS with anesthetic care were compared to means of the other questions $r = 0.41^{**}$. Reliability on test, retest $r^2 = .74^*$. PS with anesthesia care on test, retest $r = -0.19$, 95% CI [-0.41, 0.04]. All item non-responses deleted.	tests showing good content validity. ISAS measures PS. Test-retest reliability good but sensitive to time. The longer the interval between care and questionnaire, the ↓ the reliability. Limitations: ISAS for MAC only. Notes: Gold-standard test many studies reference questionnaire.

Note. ACR = Anesthesiology Consultant Report, ADL = activities of daily living, ANOVA= analysis of variance, AP = anesthesia provider, APAIS = Amsterdam Perioperative Anxiety and Information Scale, ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists, CG = control group, CI = confidence interval, combo = combination, CRNA = certified registered nurse anesthetists, CV = content validity, DV = dependent variable, EG = experimental group, ETT = endotracheal tube, eval = evaluation, EVAN-G = evaluation du vécu de l'anesthésie générale, EVAN-LR = evaluation du vécu de l'anesthésie Locorégionale, G=group (G1, G2, G3), GA = general anesthesia, GI = gastrointestinal, HA = head ache, HCW = health care workers, info = information, IC = internal consistency, I-CVI = Individual content validity, IRB = internal review board, ISAS = Iowa Satisfaction in Anesthesia Scale, IV = independent variable, LA = local anesthesia, lit = literature, LMA = laryngeal mask, LOS = length of stay, LPPSq = Leiden Perioperative care Patient Satisfaction questionnaire, MAC = monitored anesthesia care, MI = myocardial infarction, MLR = multivariate logistic regression, MGPG = McGill Pain Questionnaire, mSALT = modified Standard Anesthesia Learning Test, NMBA = neuromuscular blocking agents, OR = odds ratio, operating room, ortho = orthopedic, $*p < .05$, $**p < .001$, PA = power analysis, PACU = post-anesthesia care unit, PE = physical examination, PONV = postoperative nausea and vomiting, postop = postoperative, PQA = perception of quality in anaesthesia, PQRS = postoperative quality of recovery scale, premed = premedicated, preop = preoperative, PS=patient satisfaction, PSPACq = Perioperative Anesthetic Care questionnaire, patient(s) = pt, QA = quality assurance, QI = quality improvement, RA = regional anesthesia, RBA = risks, benefits and alternatives, re = regarding, ROL = review of literature, RN = registered nurse, S-CVI = scale content validity index, s/p = status post, SRNA = student registered nurse anesthetists, SSSQ = Satisfaction with Surgical Services Questionnaire, STAI = State Trait Anxiety Inventory, T = time, VAS = visual analog scales, vs = versus, WCCS = Wascana Client-Centered Care Survey.

Evidence Table 3. *Patient Satisfaction with Anesthesia – Qualitative Studies*

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Underpinnings & Study Design	Sample & Setting	Data Collection, Management & Analysis	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
Experiences of varicose vein surgery under LA (Hudson et al., 2015).	Qualitative mixed methods	20 pts interviewed by telephone 8 wks postop. Surgery at private clinic	Qualitative portion of mixed methods (pts included in prior RCT). Semi-structured interviews & thematic analysis from transcripts of experiences during surgery and recovery process. Coded and reconfirmed with pts.	Four themes: 1) Symptoms = negative emotions: discomfort, embarrassment, negative interaction with others, worry. (2) Cared for: relationships with nsg, pt-focused ethos of clinic, intraop distracting interventions. (3) Unprepared for surgery: lack of info, unprepared experience, unprepared for recovery. (4) Improvement in well-being: relief, positive life impact.	Conclusions: Relationships govern experience. Info given to all pts, pt attentiveness differed. Need to ensure emotional needs of pt are considered. Limitations: Study in tandem with RCT.
Perianesthesia music intervention on pt mood and satisfaction in RA (Trängeberg & Stomberg, 2013).	Multimodal: qualitative and quantitative.	15 pts, consecutive selection, undergoing elective hand procedures under RA in Gothenburg, Sweden.	Pts received axillary nerve block only, chose own music or picked from list and played throughout case. Open-ended interview questions face-to-face. Following interview, pts completed HAD. Content condensed and coded into categories by 2 authors. HAD scores analyzed using independent sample t test	Theme #1: Feeling of satisfaction. Subtheme #1: Positive experience. Subtheme #2: Inner peace (well-being, calm). Subtheme #3: Detachment from reality (alternative focus). Anxiety levels decreased following music intervention (p = .019).	Conclusions: Music helps pts ↓ anxiety during RA. Limitations: 15 pts small for quantitative portion. Length of time between procedure and interview not identified.
Pt experiences of regional ocular anesthesia for vitreo-retinal	Phenomenological/ Hermeneutical qualitative study.	18 pts interviewed after ocular anesthesia in an acute hospital	Structured interviews at pt homes & terminated when pt felt all experiences revealed. Coded thematically –	Four themes identified. 1) Not knowing: 2 grps – those that needed extensive info, those that used info to ↑ anxiety. REB = an inevitable experience.	Conclusions: REB well tolerated. Sedation may improve anxiety, but not consistently.

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Underpinnings & Study Design	Sample & Setting	Data Collection, Management & Analysis	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
surgery (McCloud et al., 2013).		in Australia	commonalities grouped into concepts and meanings then developed into themes.	Anxiety & fear. (2) Experiencing: Pain reported. Pts wanted sedation, but felt it made experience worse. (3) Knowing: If prior experience positive, anxiety ↓, if negative, anxiety ↑. (4) Enduring: Pts willing to tolerate negative experience to improve vision.	Limitations: One setting only. Mixed methods may have been helpful with quantitative component.
Experiences of patients having RA and GA for hip and knee replacement surgery (Webster et al., 2011).	Descriptive qualitative study.	12 pts with hip/knee surgery under both GA & RA at different times (last surgery within 5 yrs. Purposeful, maximum variation sampling until saturation.	Question guide – open ended reflecting on differing experiences. Interviews face-to-face and phone & transcribed verbatim. Coding done by grouping into themes.	Four themes: (1) Role of negative GA experience in preference for RA, (2) RA = quicker recovery, (3) RA => fear than GA & (4) provider preference impact. Pts chose anesthesia based on preference of anesthetist or surgeon.	Need for providers to take pt preference into account. Pts with negative GA experience, more open to RA. Fear of anesthesia and surgery. Pts did not want to hear anything in surgery. Pts concerned about being awake in surgery. Pt experience complex.
Purpose to assess PS with general and urology surgery preop, GA only, (Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010).	Design: Cross sectional, survey design with open-ended questions & qualitative component	275 pts day surgery under GA from Bristol Community Health, Lawrence Weston Clinic, United Kingdom	PS measured by questionnaire developed by researchers through qualitative study and piloted. Open-ended questions included. Mail-back responses.	3 themes: 1) preop info - ↑ info = ↑ PS & ↓ info = ↓ PS, repetitive questions and answer omissions = ↑ dissatisfaction. (2) Support – Friendliness = ↑ PS, unhelpful staff = ↓ PS (3) Anxiety & fear dominant theme - ↑ with ↓ info, ↑ with ↑ PONV, past experience shaped answers. PS: ↑ PS with ↑	Conclusions: ↑ PS through nurse-led preop assessment providing good communication & addressing anxiety. Pts expect ↑ info exchange regarding surgery, health promotion does not affect PS. Good staff attitudes ↓ fear and anxiety. Limitations: Not solely

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Underpinnings & Study Design	Sample & Setting	Data Collection, Management & Analysis	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
				communication. Reported from results of open-ended questions.	qualitative study, difficult to sift through. Large sample size, limited responses.
Purpose to assess the pt experience of the perianesthesia period; GA only (McCloud et al., 2013; Susleck et al., 2007).	Design: Phenomenological qualitative study.	10 pts recruited through purposeful snowball sampling from personal contacts.	Interviews conducted with open-ended questions. Transcripts read to group. Through data rumination, themes emerged.	Control was the dominant theme in relation to self, others and time. Control involved experience of making decisions, loss of bodily control, death, helplessness, dependence on others, relinquishing control, feeling alone, no control of time, time lost to waiting.	Conclusions: Fear of loss of control identified in other studies. Pts may feel better if well-informed, family members present, reduction of wait times, allowing pt to express emotions., Limitations: Interview setting not described
Pt perceptions of the perioperative experience; GA only (Costa, 2001).	Design: Phenomenological/ hermeneutical qualitative study.	16 pts undergoing ambulatory abdominal surgery under GA in urban teaching medical center.	Semi-structured interviews in surgeon's office 1 wk postop. Phenomenological reflection to identify themes of the experience.	3 themes: fear, knowing and presence. Fear: Fear of death, loss of control, anesthesia, fear of being cut. Knowing: Not knowing about surgical experience, being known as a person. Presence: Family/staff availability; physical and emotional.	Conclusions: Death from anesthesia = big fear. Pts need staff to listen more, talk less. ↑ info regarding postoperative expectations. Having family present alleviates anxiety/fear. Limitations: One researcher. Sample from one setting.

Note. GA = general anesthesia, gps = groups, HAD = Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, info = information, intraop = intraoperative, nsg = nursing, pt = patient(s), postop = postoperative, PS = patient satisfaction, RA = regional anesthesia, RCT = randomized controlled trial, REB = regional eye block, wks = weeks, yrs = years.

Evidence Table 4. *Consumer Satisfaction and Disconfirmation – Journal Articles*

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Framework	Sample, Setting	Measures, Definitions	Methods	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Notes
Examines the process by which consumer dissatisfaction occurs under negative expectancy disconfirmation and effect on emotions and attributions (Kim, 2014).	Disconfirmation theory specifically Negative expectancy disconfirmation	Convenience sample of students in South Korea and China	Questionnaires where consumers were first asked to recall incident where purchased product did not meet expectations. Scale from prior study measuring attribution, anger, regret and behavioral responses. Consumers rated using 7 pt Likert scale. Attributions = attitudes toward objects/events that depend on inferences made.	CFA for items and constructs showed good construct validity. Reliability $\alpha > 0.70$. Good fit index = 0.91.	External attributions show + effect on anger*. Internal attributions show + effect on regret*. Anger and regret show + effect on dissatisfaction*. Anger has + effect on complaining* and switching*. Dissatisfaction has + effect on complaining.	Consumer emotions vary according to reasons behind purchase failure. Anger produced dissatisfaction more than regret. Anger induced consumers to blame others, regret induced consumers to blame self. Extent of negative emotion varies due to cause.
Examines switching intentions, how initial and recovery disconfirmations affect consumer satisfaction after service failure followed by an offer of recovery	The expectancy/disconfirmation model to assess switching intentions after service failure and offer of recovery.	Sample from auto repair service. All repairs < \$300.00. Surveys distributed to auto shops in Taiwan from a registry.	Disconfirmation = discrepancy between expectation that service may fail and actual performance. Recovery expectations influence disconfirmation and satisfaction. Satisfaction = reflection of post-purchase assessment. Switching = dissatisfaction leads to a	Questionnaire: Expert panel, and pilot test with 30 consumers reported high validity and reliability. CFA for constructs. Good fit index = 0.95. Initial disconfirmation: 2 items. Recovery disconfirmation: 3 items. Satisfaction: 3 items. Switching intentions: 4 items.	Initial disconfirmation → satisfaction**. Recovery disconfirmation → satisfaction*. Initial & recovery have + influence on satisfaction. Satisfaction → switching**. Switching cost → switching**. Switching cost negatively associated with switching.	Good service recovery ↑ satisfaction. Consumers have ↓ tolerance for failure and expect recovery. Cost effects customer switching more than satisfaction. If dissatisfied, customers will switch when cost

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Framework	Sample, Setting	Measures, Definitions	Methods	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Notes
(Chih et al., 2012)			switch to another provider.			is lower. Suggest raising switching costs. Notes: Gives questions
Three aims leading to CD (Barnes et al., 2011)	From emotion literature. Cognitive and affective avenues to CD using disconfirmation theory	Snowball sampling of marketing students	405 surveys returned from differing industries. Differing industries divided in 3 groups. Cognitive route to delight = disconfirmation, employee effort, employee skills, core product, service recovery = CS. Affective route to delight = self-esteem (hedonistic consumption), friendliness, connectedness & attention.	Three aims: (1) develop category of affective & cognitive delight in service, (2) evaluate customer expectations of delight & (3) differences between satisfaction and delight in customer. Analysis with 3 coders resulting in classification of data	Aims (1) Customer view on delight = employee affect, effort & skill; time, core product, rule bending & service failure recovery. (2) Expectations & delight relationship = low expectations (44%) is critical factor for service fail, bad behavior, prior experience; moderate expectations (31.4%), high expectations (16.3%) = prior experience. (3) Satisfaction & delight difference = responses from (1), core product strong predictor of delight when service is focus (core product as bonus.	Service outweighs product in customer delight. Employee affect, effort & skills = customer delight. Customer reaction biggest difference between delight and satisfaction. Disconfirmation not enough, affect plays role.
Consumer regulatory focus and effect on satisfaction, prevention-focus vs promotion-focused	Regulatory focus theory prevention/promotion focus.	Random assignment. Consumers beyond disconfirmation and expectation theory. Setting:	Prevention focus – consumers concerned with security & responsibility, more sensitive to loss suggesting reluctance to make error and exhibit conservative decisions Promotion focus –	103 consumers randomly assigned to consumption experience (+ vs -) & regulatory focus (promotion vs prevention), between subjects design. Exp 1: Asked to choose between 2 cameras for	Predict that prevention focused customers less satisfied with positive outcomes and more satisfied with negative outcomes. Exp 1: Promotion focus = ↑ expectations of camera performance, not	Regulatory focus on satisfaction not part of consumer expectations, but can affect consumer expectations. Promotion

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Framework	Sample, Setting	Measures, Definitions	Methods	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Notes
consumers (Trudel et al., 2011).		North American University	concern with growth and advancement,	purchase. Promotion condition = asked consumers to think about dreams and hopes prior. Prevention condition = asked consumers to think about obligations, duties prior. 3 – pt Likert measuring pictures. Exp 2: Replicated exp 1 with coffee for validity.	significant. Prevention focus = when picture quality good, ↓ satisfaction than promotion*. Poor quality picture = ↑ satisfaction for prevention than promotion*. Exp2: Consistent results with exp 1.	customers strive higher & have higher expectations. Theory an acceptable alternative to disconfirmation.
Best predictors of CS comparing disconfirmation and Locke's model (Kanning & Bergmann, 2009)	Confirmation/Disconfirmation model and Locke's general satisfaction model.	600 questionnaires to bank customers in Germany.	Disconfirmation model: Satisfaction (s) = Expectation (e) – Performance (p). Locke = e + p + (i) importance = satisfaction.	Questionnaire dimensions: Social competence, general competence, circumstances of service, products – Likert scale.	No differences between models in 4 dimensions.	Conclusions: Locke's model does not provide better prediction of satisfaction from confirmation/disconfirmation model. Limitations: No info on psychometrics of questionnaire.
Perceived post-purchased value and relationships in loyalty behaviors (Moliner, 2008).	Conceptual theory: Agency theory – post purchase concepts of value and relationships.	Spanish private vs public hospital in Valencia, Spain.	Loyalty = commitment to hospital. Loyalty antecedents = perceived value and relationship quality. Perceived value = cognitive vs affective. Relationship quality = convenience of customer having needs met, trust	341 interviews: 171 in PrH, 170 PH using hospital services at least 3 times in 2 yrs. GLOVAL scale measuring cognitive value. Scale validity via factor analysis. Reliability = $\alpha >$ than 0.70	PH & PrH: Satisfaction influenced by perceived cognitive value. Satisfaction influences trust. Honesty influenced by quality*. PrH: Relationship quality and perceived value* = satisfaction influenced by cognitive value, and cost.	Conclusions: Antecedents of loyalty: commitment, satisfaction, trust, benevolence: Satisfaction most important. Satisfaction/loyalty closely

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Framework	Sample, Setting	Measures, Definitions	Methods	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Notes
			& satisfaction. GLOVAL scale = 16 items measuring quality, staff professionalism, installations & cost.	in satisfaction, investment, professionalism, quality of service. trust & costs.		linked. Limitations: Factor analysis, but some items with only one dimension. Loyalty influenced by process. Notes: Questions listed.
Personal values vs cost better antecedent of service satisfaction (Bloemer & Dekker, 2007).	The value disparity-disconfirmation model adapted from the synthesis of the value percept disparity and disconfirmation model.	439 randomly selected customers from 18 bank branches in Belgium.	CS via disconfirmation model = expectations compared with performance = confirmation or disconfirmation. Values = internal vs external: Internal = more self-fulfillment needing more control, external = belonging/security value others in environment. Value disparity/disconfirmation model – $S = f(CPSV, CV, CESV)$	CS measured with 3 item, 9 pt Likert scale, $\alpha = 0.87$. EVD = expected employee values minus expected customer values both internal and external. PVD = customer value dimension minus the customer precept service value dimension. Random effects model analysis on all bank employee/customer levels.	Value disparity (expected and perceived effect CS**). Negative effect of EVD (-0.184*) on internal values. Negative effect on EVD on external values (-0.446*). External values only significant when assessing external and internal dimensions together.	Disconfirmation model supported best. Value percept disparity model not supported. Customer values not linked to CS. Customer values may shape expectations. Notes: Tough one.
Actual, expected and perceived waiting and CS (Ellis et al., 2005).	Expectancy disconfirmation model of CS.	Exp 1: 105 business students at Aachen University, Germany &	Perceived pre-process wait time = subjective estimation of time waiting prior to service. Expectations from prior experience.	Exp 1: Service = prep of a tech report. Expected wait = subjects told would wait 5 or 20 min. Subjects actually waited 3, 10 or 30 min.	Exp 1: Expectations have negative effect*, perceptions had a positive effect* Exp 2: Same as exp. 1.	↑ disconfirmation with service = ↓ CS. Pre-process wait times can

Aims (Source)	Conceptual Framework	Sample, Setting	Measures, Definitions	Methods	Results Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Notes
		Switzerland Exp 2: 12 faculty and PhD students in Sydney, Australia		Results from questionnaire with 7 pt Likert scale. Exp 2: Subjects told would wait 4 min, actual wait 3-7 min.		improve overall experience with service. Quality of service perception ↑ with ↑ preprocess wait.
Integration of attribute experience with disconfirmation theory for new CS framework, tested with consumers (Oliver, 1993).	CS/D based on disconfirmation theory. Added dimension of positive and negative attributes.	Consumers' decisions regarding repeat purchase of products.	AS = consumer's subjective judgment as psychological response of performance assessment. Negative affect includes internal, external and product sources. Affect measured by DES scale. AS measured from 19 attributes from focus groups. Satisfaction measured with 12-item Likert scale.	5 Hs: (1) Affect response + (joy, interest) or – (internal, external, situation/product) dimension, (2) AS influences + & – affect, (3) AS/AD affects service satisfaction judgments, (4) + & - affect influences service judgment, (5) disconfirmation related to satisfaction. 2 field studies.	H ₁ not supported for + affect. H ₂ supported, + affect attributed to AS, but – affect not attributed to AD*. H ₃ supported** H ₄ & H ₅ supported* Attributes, affects and disconfirmation form basis of perception of satisfaction.	AS affects overall satisfaction, + affect. AD affects - affect. + and – affect, are + and – influences respectively on satisfaction. Disconfirmation requires deliberate info processing; affect not conscious.

Note. AS = attribute satisfaction, AD = attribute dissatisfaction, CD = customer delight, CESV = customer expected service values, CFA = confirmatory factor analysis, CPSV = customer perceived service values, CS = consumer/customer satisfaction, CS/D = consumer satisfaction/dissatisfaction, CV = customer values, DES = differential emotions scale, EVD = expected value disparity, Exp = experiment, H = hypothesis, info = information, min = minute, *p < .05, **p < .001, PH = public hospital, prep = preparation, PrH = private hospital, pt = point, PVD = perceived value disparity, S = satisfaction, tech = technology, vs = versus, yr = years.

Evidence Table 5. *Satisfaction – Concept Analysis*

Purpose (Source)	Framework	Data Sources	Definitions	Attributes/Dimensions	Results; Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Notes
Concept analysis of nursing care (Wagner & Bear, 2008).	IMCHB – to assess pt characteristics in order to optimize pt interaction and improve outcomes influenced by affective support, info, decision control, competence. CA: 1) ID interest, (2) data collection, (3) collect data, (4) analyze data, (5) ID example, (6) ID implications.	Cumulative Index of Nursing CINAHL MEDLINE Allied Health Lit. ABI/INFORM	PS: Congruence between expectations and care. Attributes: True concept definition. Affective support: Calm fears. Health info: Info on health, lifestyle impact, health threats, ↑ info = ↑ PS. Decisional control: Pt participation in health decision-making. Professionalism: Technical skills, PS ↑ with competence and clinical knowledge. Antecedents: Concept prerequisites – pt characteristics (motivation, cognition, affect), prior experience, demographics, social structure, culture and environment. Consequences: Outcomes – service utilization & adherence to care.	PS with nursing: Interpersonal care, humaneness, technical quality, competence, convenience, cost, environment, provider availability, continuity, outcomes.	IMCHB clarifies PS. Helpful to explore pt motivation. Individualized care ↑ PS.	Framework to define PS. IMCHB accounts for pt unique characteristics and unique nurse/pt relationship.

Purpose (Source)	Framework	Data Sources	Definitions	Attributes/Dimensions	Results; Theoretical Integration	Authors' Conclusions; Notes
Concept clarification of PS (Eriksen, 1995).	Conceptual clarification: 1) ID concept, (2) Lit search (3) attribute listing, (4) ID antecedents and consequences, (4) referents for attributes,	Dictionary PS lit CS lit	Satisfaction: Contentment, pleasure, gratification, fulfill expectations. PS with medical care: 1) Provider success of meeting pt expectation. (2) Pt reaction to service experience. (3) + emotional response from cognitive process comparing personal standard to experience. PS with nursing: 1) Congruence between expectations and perceptions of care. (2) Inner state reflection good feelings about care. CS: 1) How well service/product meets needs. (2) Consumer expectations followed by evaluation and comparison of experience. (3) A judgment made by the consumer.	PS with medical care: thoroughness, information, courtesy, friendliness, concern & respect. CS: Expectations, outcomes, processes, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy. PS: Technical quality, delivery of care, nursing behavior, kindness, cheerfulness, courteous, friendly, communication, concern, explanation, professional image, acceptance,	Satisfaction not as a continuum; either satisfied or dissatisfied. Satisfaction judged from prior experience. Lower expectations = higher satisfaction. Defining attributes of PS: pt expectations, cognitive/emotional response, manner in which care is delivered, evaluation of experience	Conclusions: Appropriate domains critical for measurement of concept. With no continuum, may need separate measurement for PS and PD. Limitations: Not much info on lit review.

Note. CA = concept analysis, CS = consumer satisfaction, ID = identify, IMCHB = Interaction Model of Client Health Behavior, info = information, lit = literature, PD = patient dissatisfaction, PS = patient satisfaction, pt = patient.

APPENDIX D

ITEM DIMENSIONS AND CONSTRUCTS LEADING TO DISSATISFACTION

Authors	Pain	PONV	↓ info	RBA explain	Questions not answered	Fear/ Anxiety	AC	↑ Wait times	↓ IDM	↑ Surgical Length	IA	ASA I&II	Female	Age >55	↑ Edu
1	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓								
2	✓		✓			✓		✓							
3									✓						
4	✓	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	
5	✓			✓		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓	
6	✓	✓				✓				✓					
7				✓	✓				✓					✓	
8															✓
9												✓	✓		✓
10						✓									
11	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓							
12	✓			✓		✓						✓	✓		✓
13				✓	✓	✓									
14						✓							✓	✓	
15	✓					✓		✓		✓				✓	✓
16	✓		✓									✓		✓	
17		✓	✓			✓									
18	✓	✓				✓		✓							
19	✓	✓	✓												
20	✓	✓													
21			✓												
22	✓	✓					✓			✓	✓		✓	✓	
23				✓			✓								
24	✓	✓				✓									

Note. AC = anesthesia complications, Edu = education IA = intraoperative awareness, IDM = involvement in decision making, PONV = postoperative nausea and vomiting, RBA = risks, benefits and alternatives, 1 = (Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014), 2 = (R. Hawkins et al., 2014), 3 = (Flierler et al., 2013), 4 = (Hocking et al., 2013), 5 = (Maurice-Szamburski et al., 2013), 6 = (Royse et al., 2013), 7 = (Puro et al., 2013), 8 = (Shahrokh Iravani et al., 2012), 9 = (Saal et al., 2011), 10 = (Mitchell, 2011), 11 = (Mui et al., 2011), 12 = (Baroudi et al., 2010), 13 = (Fraczyk & Godfrey, 2010), 14 = (Caljouw et al., 2008), 15 = (Shiff et al., 2008), 16 = Auquier et al., 2005), 17 = (Capuzzo et al., 2005), 18 = (McCarthy et al., 2004), 19 = (Bauer et al., 2001), 20 = (Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001), 21 = (Fung & Cohen, 2001), 22 = (Myles et al., 2000), 23 = (Fleisher et al., 1999), 24 = (Dexter et al., 1997)

APPENDIX E

TABLE: ITEMS AND CONCEPT DOMAINS FROM PATIENT SATISFACTION SURVEYS

Domain	Items	Source	
Information sharing	The information provided to me about my anesthesia plan and care had adequate detail. The information provided to me about my anesthesia plan was easy to understand. I was given enough time to understand the anesthesia plan.	(Hawkins, Swanson, Kremer, & Fogg, 2014)	
	The information was given in a pleasant environment. The informing doctor should be friendlier. The anesthesiologist did not give enough information. The information given was understandable.	(Schiff et al., 2008)	
	During the preoperative visits with the anesthesiologist, I received information about what was going to happen....I was able to ask questions I wanted. I received preoperative information about what was to happen from the surgeon.	(Maurice-Szamburski, Bruder, Loundou, Capdevila, & Auquier, 2013)	
	To what degree were you satisfied with the opportunities for you to ask the questions about anesthesia? To what degree were you satisfied with the answers of the anesthesiologists about your questions? To what degree were you satisfied with the amount of information given from the anesthesiologists? To what degree were you satisfied with the opportunities to inform the anesthesiologists about your previous anesthesia experience?	(Mui et al., 2011)	
	Fasting instructions given	Information about anesthesia type given	(Dexter, Aker, & Wright,

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>Information about postoperative complications given</p> <hr/> <p>Please rate your satisfaction with the explanation about anesthesia. Please rate your satisfaction with the amount of information about anesthesia.</p> <p>Please rate your satisfaction about the explanation about the operation. Please rate your satisfaction regarding the amount of information about the operation.</p> <p>Please rate your satisfaction about the explanation of your stay at the operating theatre. Please rate your satisfaction about the amount of information about your stay in the operating theatre</p>	<p>1997)</p> <hr/> <p>(Jlala et al., 2010)</p>
Information sharing	<p>To what degree were you satisfied about:</p> <p>The explanation about the operation? The amount of information about the operation? The explanation about your stay at the operating room theatre? The amount of information about your stay at the operating theatre centre?</p>	<p>(Caljouw et al., 2008; Jlala et al., 2010)</p>
	<p>I had a good understanding of the way in which the anesthetic worked. Anesthetic issues that were important to me were addressed thoroughly. I had a clear understanding of the purpose and/or goals of the anesthetic. I was given the opportunity to participate in setting my anesthetic treatment goals. I was given adequate information about the anesthetic. I have a good understanding of information provided regarding my anesthetic. My unanswered questions and needs were addressed regarding the</p>	<p>(Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001)</p>

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>anesthetic.</p> <p>Information about my anesthetic care was provided in a nonthreatening manner.</p> <p>My family and friends received information to assist me following my anesthetic.</p> <p>Tests and procedures related to the anesthetic were adequately explained.</p> <p>My questions about the anesthetic were acknowledged.</p>	
	<p>The anesthesiologist identifies all my concerns, encourages me to communicate those concerns and then answers all my questions.</p> <p>The anesthesiologist or nurse tells me about the possible minor side effects of anesthesia.</p> <p>The anesthesiologist discusses the anesthetic care with me and involves me in the decision of what particular anesthetic is best for me.</p> <p>I am informed about the rare serious risks and dangers about anesthesia.</p> <p>I have received clear and adequate instructions about how to manage my own care at home.</p> <p>I am told about the minor or major discomforts and inconveniences that I might feel after the operation.</p> <p>I have a phone number of someone to contact if there is something I become worried about.</p> <p>I am able to obtain explanations about unexpected side effects and complications.</p>	(D. Fung & Cohen, 2001)
	<p>During this hospital stay, how often did doctors listen carefully to you?</p> <p>During this hospital stay, how often did doctors explain things in a way you could understand?</p>	(HCAHPS, 2014)

Domain	Items	Source	
Concern and kindness of providers	My anesthesia provider showed concern toward me during my anesthesia care. My anesthesia provider showed kindness toward me during my anesthesia care.	(Hawkins, Swanson, Kremer, & Fogg, 2014)	
	Were you treated kindly by the staff of the operating theatre centre?	(Caljouw et al., 2008)	
	Anesthesia staff in the recovery room or intensive care were friendly. You can trust the anesthesia staff.	(Schiff et al., 2008)	
	I was treated with dignity and respect by the anesthesiologist. My anesthesiologist was caring and supportive. People important to me were treated with respect by the anesthesiologist. The anesthesiologist tried to ensure my comfort. The nurses and doctors are friendly, helpful and compassionate. The anesthesiologist is kind, friendly and gentle. The nurses are caring, helpful and do not rush me home. The hospital phones me in the first 72 hours to see how I'm doing.	(Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001)	
	During this hospital stay, how often did doctors treat you with courtesy and respect?	(HCAHPS, 2014)	
	Interpersonal skills of providers/attention	The demeanor of the anesthesia provider was beneficial to my anesthesia care. The communication skills of the anesthesia provider were beneficial to my anesthesia care	(Hawkins, Swanson, Kremer, & Fogg, 2014)
		My anesthesia provider gave me adequate attention during anesthesia care. I felt safe during my anesthesia care. I felt a sense of well-being during my anesthesia care.	

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>Upon OR admission, medical staff was attentive. In the recovery room, medical and nursing staffs were attentive. Since I came back in my bedroom, nursing staff was attentive. My privacy was respected.</p> <p>To what degree were you satisfied with the anesthesia service that the anesthetists were respectful? To what degree were you satisfied with the anesthesia service that the anesthetists were willing to pay attention to your conditions?</p> <p>To what degree were you satisfied with the anesthesia service that the anesthetists were willing to listen to your questions?</p> <p>To what degree were you satisfied with the anesthesia service that the anesthetists had considered your privacy? To what degree were you satisfied with the anesthesia service that the anesthetists were knowledgeable and professional?</p>	<p>(Maurice-Szamburski, Bruder, Loundou, Capdevila, & Auquier, 2013)</p>
	<p>Were the staff attentive to your needs?</p> <p>Did they act according to your needs?</p> <p>Did they consult another health professional?</p> <p>Did the theatre staff take into account your privacy?</p> <p>Did you have confidence in the theatre staff?</p> <p>Had the theatre staff an open attitude?</p> <p>Were the theatre staff respectful?</p> <p>Did the theatre staff show understanding for your situation?</p> <p>Were the theatre staff polite?</p> <p>Did you find the theatre staff professional?</p> <p>Did the theatre staff pay attention to your questions?</p> <p>Did the theatre staff pay attention to complaints like pain and nausea?</p>	<p>(Jlala et al., 2010)</p>

Domain	Items	Source
Interpersonal skills of providers/attention	<p>Did the theatre staff take into account your personnel preferences?</p> <p>Did you find the theatre staff knowledgeable?</p> <p>Did the theatre staff pay attention to you as an individual?</p> <p>Were you treated kindly by the theatre staff?</p> <p>Did you experience professional competence?</p> <hr/> <p>Did the staff of the operating theatre centre take into account your privacy?</p> <p>Did you have confidence in the staff of the operating theatre centre?</p> <p>Had the staff of the operating theatre centre an open attitude?</p> <p>Were the staff of the operating theatre centre show understanding for your situation?</p> <p>Were the staff of the operating theatre centre polite?</p> <p>Did you find the staff of the operating theatre centre professional?</p> <p>Did the staff of the operating theater centre pay attention to your questions?</p> <p>Did the staff of the operating theatre centre pay attention to your complaints like pain and nausea?</p> <p>Did the staff of the operating theatre centre take into account your personnel references?</p> <p>Did staff of the operating theatre centre take into account your cultural background?</p> <p>Did you find the staff of the operating theatre centre knowledgeable?</p> <p>Did staff of the operating theatre centre pay attention to you as an individual?</p>	<p>(Caljouw et al., 2008)</p>

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>My treatment needs, priorities and goals were important to the anesthesiologist.</p> <p>I had adequate contact with my anesthesiologist.</p> <p>I felt comfortable participating in activities related to my anesthetic care.</p> <p>I felt at ease with the care provided by the anesthesiologist.</p> <p>I felt comfortable expressing my worries to the anesthesiologist.</p>	(Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001)
	<p>My fears and anxieties about the surgery are handled appropriately beforehand.</p> <p>The anesthesiologist talks to me as they ready me for the anesthetic.</p> <p>I feel confidence and trust in the anesthesiologist and nurses looking after me.</p> <p>The anesthesiologist is efficient and unhurried in his or her manner.</p> <p>The anesthesiologist respects my needs and requests.</p> <p>The nurses are able to respond to my needs or requests quickly.</p>	(D. Fung & Cohen, 2001)
Addressing pain, discomfort, other physical peri-operative needs	<p>My pain control during and after surgery was adequate. The anesthesia provider addressed my pain control.</p> <p>I was nauseous after my anesthetic. The anesthesia provider addressed my nausea and vomiting control.</p>	(Hawkins, Swanson, Kremer, & Fogg, 2014)
	<p>During surgery, I had unpleasant feelings like thirst, hunger, nausea, headache. I felt uncomfortable hearing and/or seeing what was happening. After surgery I had unpleasant feelings like thirst, hunger, nausea and headache. I felt uncomfortable, cold, warm, badly postured on the bed.</p>	(Maurice-Szamburski, Bruder, Loundou, Capdevila, & Auquier, 2013)
	<p>To what degree after the operation did you feel afraid of: Pain?</p>	(Jlala et al., 2010)

Domain	Items	Source
	Sore throat? Back pain? Nausea? Vomiting? Cold? Hunger? Thirst? Headache?	
Addressing pain, discomfort, other physical peri-operative needs	<hr/> To what degree did you after the operation have: Postoperative pain? A sore throat? Back pain? Vomiting? Cold? Hunger? Thirst?	(Caljouw et al., 2008)
	<hr/> After receiving the anesthesia service, to what degree were you afraid of pain because of the anesthetic? To what degree were you discomforted by too cold or too warm perioperatively? To what degree were you feeling discomforted by thirsty or hungry perioperatively? To what degree were you feeling discomforted by the posture on the operating table? To what degree were you feeling discomforted by nausea and vomiting perioperatively?	(Mui et al., 2011)

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>Thirst before anesthesia was a problem.</p> <p>Feeling cold and shivering was experienced in the room where anesthesia was applied.</p> <p>Pain prior to the anesthesia caused stress.</p> <p>Waking up from anesthesia was comfortable.</p> <p>Little or no pain was experienced in other areas following the surgery.</p> <p>Staff members were seriously concerned about my pain.</p> <p>The staff quickly alleviated my pain.</p> <p>Nausea or vomiting was a problem following anesthesia.</p> <p>Hoarseness or sore throat was a problem following anesthesia.</p> <p>Weakness of the muscles was a problem following anesthesia.</p> <p>Thirst was a problem following anesthesia.</p> <p>An urgent need to urinate was a problem following anesthesia.</p> <p>Feeling cold or shivering were problems following the anesthesia.</p> <p>It was hard to breath following the anesthesia.</p> <p>Fatigue or inability to concentrate was a problem following anesthesia.</p>	<p>(Schiff et al., 2008)</p>
	<p>My reports of pain were acknowledged by the anesthesiologist.</p> <p>My pain was controlled in a satisfactory manner by the anesthesiologist.</p> <p>I had adequate time for rest and sleep following the anesthetic.</p> <p>My physical surroundings were comfortable with respect to the anesthetic.</p> <p>I experienced no negative side effects of the anesthetic.</p> <p>There were no complications related to the anesthetic.</p>	<p>(Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001)</p>

Domain	Items	Source	
Addressing psychological peri-operative needs	I experience little or no immediate side effects like nausea, vomiting, pain, dizziness or sore throat. I have no or few side effects. I am able to resume normal activities right away.	(D. Fung & Cohen, 2001)	
	I threw up or felt like throwing up I itched I felt pain I was too cold or hot I felt pain during surgery	(Dexter, Aker, & Wright, 1997)	
	During this hospital stay, how well was your pain well controlled? During this hospital stay, how often did the hospital staff do everything they could to help you with your pain?	(HCAHPS, 2014)	
	I was fearful about my anesthetic. The anesthesia provider addressed my fears/anxiety about my anesthetic.	(Hawkins, Swanson, Kremer, & Fogg, 2014)	
	Patient felt less anxious after anesthetist visit	(Gebremedhn & Nagaratnam, 2014)	
	After receiving the anesthesia service, to what degree were you afraid of seeing the operating room again?	(Mui et al., 2011)	
	To what degree after the operation did you feel afraid of: Awaking during the operation? Seeing the operating room? Pain due to surgery? Pain due to anesthetic?	(Jlala et al., 2010)	
	To what degree were you afraid of: Not awaking after the operation? Awaking during the operation?	(Caljouw et al., 2008)	
	Addressing psychological peri-operative needs		

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>Seeing the operating room? Pain due to the surgeon? Mistakes by the surgeon? Pain due to the anesthetist? Mistakes by the anesthetist? Was the staff attentive to your needs? Did they act according to your needs? Did they consult another health professional? To what degree did you experience professional competence?</p>	
	<p>The anesthetist doctor appeared to be under time pressure during the consultation. Fear of anesthesia played an important role. Fear of surgery played an important role. The night before surgery felt relaxed. Prior to the procedure fear to the point of losing control was felt. The feeling of being left alone caused stress. In general fear or agitation played an important role in the time prior to anesthesia. The atmosphere was pleasant in the anesthesia room. Staff members took good care of and were responsive when anesthesia was applied. The recovery following anesthesia went well.</p>	<p>(Schiff et al., 2008)</p>
	<p>The anesthetic was an important part of my surgery for me and my family. I felt I was ready for my discharge to the unit or home following the anesthetic.</p>	<p>(Hadjistavropoulos et al., 2001)</p>

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>My need for privacy was respected by the anesthesiologist I was able to express my feelings freely to the anesthesiologist. My emotional needs (worries) were taken seriously by the anesthesiologist.</p> <hr/> <p>My family or support member was allowed to be with me before the surgery. I feel calm and relaxed. The anesthesiologist is always present to assure my safety while I am asleep. I feel safe throughout my recovery from the anesthetic. My family or support person is allowed to be with me as soon as I am awake. I am thinking normally and clearly as soon as I wake up from the anesthetic. I have enough help at home.</p> <hr/> <p>I felt relaxed I felt safe</p>	<p>(D. Fung & Cohen, 2001)</p> <p>(Dexter, Aker, & Wright, 1997)</p>
Waiting time adequacy	<p>To what degree were you satisfied with the waiting time in the whole process of the anesthesia service? To what degree were you satisfied with the waiting time for the postoperative pain management service?</p> <hr/> <p>The waiting time between leaving the ward and having your operation was too long, long, just right, short?</p> <p>The waiting time spent in the recovery room and getting back to the ward was too long, long, just right, short?</p> <p>Were you operated on the agreed date and time?</p>	<p>(Mui et al., 2011)</p> <p>(Jlala et al., 2010)</p>

Domain	Items	Source
	<p>Were you operated on the agreed date and time?</p> <p>How did you experience the waiting time between your arrival at the operating theatre centre and the operation?</p> <p>How did you experience the waiting time between your time spend in the recovery room and your leaving of the operating theatre centre?</p> <p>There are little to no delays and everything proceeded like clockwork in an orderly, predictable and smooth manner.</p> <p>All the hospital areas that I visit to get me ready for surgery are easy to find, convenient to get around and comfortable to be in.</p> <p>I am able to leave the hospital in a matter of hours.</p>	(Caljouw et al., 2008)
	<p>The waiting time before the consultation of the anaesthetist for informed consent was too long.</p> <p>The surgery was postponed for another day.</p> <p>The wait time the morning before surgery was long.</p>	(Schiff et al., 2008)